

**Palestine Polytechnic University
College of Engineering
Department Of Mechanical Engineering**

**Design and building a scalable low power PV-based private
EV/PHEV charging system**

Project Team:

Abdallah Aref Shawamreh

Mohammad Midyan Jazi

Ayman Hider Swaity

Supervisor: Dr. Momen Sughayyer

**Submitted to the College of Engineering and Technology
in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the
Bachelor's degree in Automotive Engineering
Palestine Polytechnic University**

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الاهداء

الى

معلم البشرية ومنبع العلم نبينا محمد (صلى الله عليه وسلم)

فلسطين الحبيبة الى غزة الصامدة الى

الى مثل الابوة الاعلى والدي العزيز

الى حبيبة قلبي الاولى امي الحنونة

الى الحب كل الحب اخوتي واخواتي

الى كافة الاهل والاصدقاء

الى من مهدوا الطريق امامي للوصول الى ذروة العلم

اهدي هذا الجهد المتواضع

. الى من اعطونا النقاط لنضعها على الحروف

الى من نفخوا من افواههم الكلمات لنصنع بها مستقبل زاهر

اساتذتي الافاضل

لكم جميعاً

شكر و تقدير

ليس هناك شكر أعظم من الاعتراف بالجميل، وليس هناك مشكور أعظم من صاحب الفضل الذي لا ينقطع فضله ولا تُعدّ نعمه، فحمدًا لله حمدًا لا ينتهي عند حد ولا ينقطع عند أجل، فهو الموفق والهادي إلى سواء السبيل. وفي هذا المقام المهيب، لا يسعنا إلا أن نرفع أسمى عبارات الشكر والتقدير، ونُعبر عن بالغ امتناننا وعظيم عرفاننا لكل من أسهم في إنجاز هذا البحث، متحدين معنا الصعاب، ومساندين لنا خطوة بخطوة، حتى تحقق هذا العمل العلمي بالشكل الذي نرتضيه ويرتقي إلى تطلعاتنا.

نخص بالذكر أستاذنا الفاضل، الدكتور مؤمن صغير، المشرف والموجه والقُدوة، الذي لم يتوان ولم يتأخر يومًا عن تقديم ما آتاه الله من علم وخبرة، فكان لنا نعم الداعم ونعم المرشد. كما لا يفوتنا أن نشيد بجهود طاقم دائرة الهندسة الميكانيكية، كلٌّ باسمه ومكانته، على تفانيهم ومثابرتهم ودعمهم الذي أضاء لنا سنوات دراستنا.

ولا يسعنا إلا أن نوجه تحية تقدير خاصة لزملائنا الأعزاء، الذين كان لوجودهم بيننا طعمٌ خاص؛ فهم شركاء المسيرة وملهمو المنافسة الإيجابية، ولولاهم لما شعرنا بمتعة البحث ولا بحلاوة الإنجاز.

كما نتقدم بجزيل الشكر والامتنان إلى الشركات الداعمة، التي قدّمت لنا دعمًا حقيقيًا نُثمنه عاليًا، وهم:

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٢. شركة إيني تايين.

٣. شركة مصادر للطاقة.

٤. متجر ديكو فلسطين.

٥. شركة زياد الحداد.

٦. م. عبدالله شاهين.

٧. مركز التطوير والبحث العلمي -جامعه بوليتكنك فلسطين.

٨. شركة التكامل الهندسية.

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وختام القول مسك، فكل الشكر وكل الامتنان لآبائنا وأمهاتنا وإخواننا، الذين كانوا لنا السند الحقيقي والدافع الأكبر للوصول إلى هذه اللحظة، ونسأل الله أن نكون قد وفيناهم جزءًا من حقهم ببلوغنا رضاهم وفخرهم.

Abstract

This project presents the design, implementation, and successful testing of an off-grid, scalable, solar-powered charging station for Electric Vehicles (EVs) and Plug-in Hybrid Electric Vehicles (PHEVs), installed within the campus of Palestine Polytechnic University.

The system integrates photovoltaic panels, an inverter, battery storage, and an EV charger to enable efficient and sustainable vehicle charging independent of the conventional power grid.

After installation, the station was successfully tested and used to charge an electric vehicle.

The project demonstrates the feasibility of establishing clean energy infrastructure on a small scale within academic institutions.

This station contributes to reducing carbon emissions, promoting renewable energy adoption, and serves as an educational and research platform supporting innovative solutions for sustainable and smart mobility

التلخيص

يعرض هذا المشروع تصميم، تنفيذ، واختبار محطة شحن تعمل بالطاقة الشمسية، منفصلة عن شبكة الكهرباء (Off-grid) ، ومخصصة لشحن كلٍ من المركبات الكهربائية (EVs) والمركبات الهجينة القابلة للشحن (PHEVs)، وقد تم تركيبها داخل حرم جامعة بوليتكنك فلسطين.

يتكون النظام من ألواح شمسية، إنفرتر، بطاريات لتخزين الطاقة، وجهاز شحن للمركبات الكهربائية، وتم اختبار المحطة بنجاح واستخدامها لشحن سيارة كهربائية.

يوضح المشروع إمكانية إنشاء بنية تحتية نظيفة ومستقلة داخل المؤسسات التعليمية على نطاق محدود. وقد ركز التصميم على قابلية التوسع مستقبلاً، وكفاءة استخدام الطاقة، واستقرار النظام تحت ظروف بيئية مختلفة. تسهم هذه المحطة في تقليل الانبعاثات الكربونية، وتشجيع الاعتماد على الطاقة المتجددة، كما تُعد منصة تعليمية وبحثية لدعم حلول التنقل الذكي والمستدام.

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CHAPTER ONE

PROJECT CONCEPT

1.1 Overview

This project introduces an off-grid electrical charging station, designed to provide a self-sufficient, sustainable, and cost-effective solution for charging electric vehicles (EVs) and plug-in hybrid electric vehicles (PHEVs). Leveraging photovoltaic (PV) technology as the sole power source, this system eliminates dependency on traditional grid electricity while ensuring energy independence and environmental benefits. By combining cutting-edge solar technology, efficient energy storage, and smart load management, the charging station delivers a reliable and scalable solution tailored for private or small-scale networked use. Ideal for rural areas, remote locations, or spaces with limited grid access, the system supports uninterrupted operation during low sunlight and offers a future-proof infrastructure for sustainable transportation.

1.2 Research Problem

The deployment of Electric Vehicles (EVs) needs rapid acceleration to meet electric energy demand, but challenges like grid capacity and infrastructure issues hinder progress. Addressing these challenges through integrated solutions can benefit both EV and PV deployment. This project introduction on integrating solar energy with Plug-in Hybrid Electric Vehicle (PHEV) charging. It aims to design a solar-powered charging system that reduces grid dependency. The study includes an analysis of energy requirements, solar panel performance, and a cost-benefit evaluation of long-term savings. The system's scalability supports future expansion and promotes awareness of renewable energy's benefits where individuals manage their own energy needs using rooftop solar and EV charging. This integration helps lower dependency on grid, optimizes renewable energy use, and supports the transition toward a sustainable future by demonstrating the feasibility and benefits of solar-powered EV charging in Palestine.

1.3 Objectives

The main objective of this project is to provide a holistic approach to build a solar-powered charging system. By focusing on design, energy analysis, financial viability, technological integration, feasibility the project seeks to promote sustainable energy

solutions in the automotive sector, contributing to a cleaner and more sustainable future. Additionally, this project aims to facilitate the transition to electric vehicles. The specific objectives are as follows:

1. Solar Energy System Design: Design an integrated solar energy system that charges Hybrid \Electric Vehicle (EV).
2. Energy Consumption Analysis: Determine the amount of energy required to charge the car and analyze the productivity of solar panels.

By addressing these objectives, the project will provide insights into the potential for solar energy to facilitate the transition to electric vehicles and enhance sustainability in the transport sector in Palestine.

1.4 Project Importance

This project enables facilitates adoption and use by using solar energy to charge Plug-in Hybrid Electric Vehicles (PHEVs). It reduces depends on Israel sources, lowers emissions, and cuts costs. By empowering individuals to generate their own solar energy, it supports a cleaner, more efficient energy system, accelerating the shift to low-carbon transport.

1.5 Project Requirements

The main objective of this project is to establish a clear set of requirements that are crucial for its successful implementation

1. Solar Panels: High-efficiency panels for capturing energy.
2. Inverter: Converts DC solar power to AC for charging.
3. EV Charging Station: Compatible with PHEV charging needs.
4. Battery Storage: Stores excess energy for use during low sunlight.

1.6 Project Methodology

1. Energy Analysis: Determine the energy needs for fully charging the PHEV battery and assess solar panel output based on location and weather conditions.

2. System Design: Select and integrate solar panels, inverters, battery storage, and a compatible EV charging station to optimize energy conversion and storage.
3. Installation and Setup: Install the solar panels, inverters, and charging infrastructure, ensuring proper alignment and connection for maximum efficiency.
4. Financial Assessment: Conduct a cost-benefit analysis, comparing initial investment with long-term savings in fuel and electricity.

1.7 System Architecture of Solar-Powered EV Charging

The proposed charging system integrates photovoltaic (PV) modules with power electronics and storage to ensure stable and continuous charging for battery electric vehicles (BEVs). Solar energy is first collected by the PV panels and directed to the DC box, which manages the direct current flow. An inverter converts DC into AC, enabling compatibility with the grid and vehicle charging equipment. The AC box distributes power safely to the charger, which regulates voltage and current before delivering energy to the car's battery. Additionally, an energy storage battery is connected at the DC stage to store excess solar energy and supply it during periods of low irradiance or at night, ensuring system reliability and energy autonomy.

Figure 1 .1 Energy Flow Diagram of Solar EV Charging System

1.8 Plan Implementation

Task 1: Selecting a suitable idea aligned with the project's goals and scope.

Task 2: Gathering data and researching past studies, as well as comprehending the project's core concept.

Task 3: Studying prior research, collecting, and reviewing existing studies to understand the project's background and context.

Task 4: Writing the introduction section of the graduation project, ensuring clarity and relevance.

Task 5: Preparing and presenting the introduction as part of the spring semester 2023/2024 evaluation.

Task 6: Revising and improving the project introduction to reflect updated goals, approaches, and technical adjustments.

Task 7: Securing financial and material support to cover most of the project's costs, ensuring smooth implementation without budget shortfalls.

Task 8: Writing and developing portions of the final project report, especially the sections related to design, methodology, and technical analysis.

Task 9: Assembling the system components, installing the full setup, and conducting comprehensive tests to validate performance and ensure all systems function correctly.

Task 10: Editing, finalizing, and writing the complete project report, ensuring professional presentation and technical accuracy

Table 1.1 First semester Action plan 2024/2025

Week \ Task	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
Task 1	█	█	█													
Task 2		█	█	█	█											
Task 3			█	█	█	█	█	█								
Task 4						█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█		
Task 5												█	█	█	█	█

Table 1.2 Second semester Action plan 2024/2025

Week \ Task	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
Task 6	█	█	█	█	█	█										
Task 7			█	█	█	█	█	█	█							
Task 8						█	█	█	█	█	█	█				
Task 9								█	█	█	█	█	█	█		
Task 10													█	█	█	█

1.8 Project cost

Initial Cost estimation & calculation are listed in Table (1.3) below:

Table 0.3 Cost Estimation

Item	Quantity	Unit Cost (NIS)	Total Cost (NIS)	
Solar Panels	7	600	4200	Donation (Enetine Energy)
Battery Storage	2	300	600	
Inverter	1	6000	6000	Donation (Optimus Group)
Charger	1	5000	5000	Donation (Optimus Group)
Square, Profile Beam	5	500	500	Donation (Ziad Alhaddad Group)
BMS	1	800	800	Donation (DEKO Palestine Store)
Circuit Breakers	—	600	600	Donation (Massader)
Electrical Cabinet	—	300	300	
Solar Panel Cables	—	300	300	Donation (Masader)
Wiring	—	100	200	
Iron Paint	—	30	30	
Fire Extinguishers	—	200	200	
Cooling Fans	5	20	100	
Transportation	--	--	500	
screws	--	--	50	
Blacksmithing and welding works	--	--	200	
Mc4	--	--	50	
Print the project	--	--	150	
Total			19,230₪	

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

The integration of solar energy into charging infrastructure for battery electric vehicles (BEVs) constitutes a pivotal advancement toward enhancing energy sustainability and mitigating greenhouse gas emissions. This development is particularly critical in the context of Palestine, where environmental degradation and geopolitical instability underscore the need for resilient and self-sufficient energy solutions. Solar-powered charging systems offer a promising outlook, especially in facilitating energy autonomy and minimizing environmental harm.

Although electric vehicles (EVs) are fundamentally designed to curtail emissions, reduce urban air pollution, and decrease reliance on fossil fuels, the actual environmental impact depends significantly on the source of electricity used for charging. In many regions, including Palestine, electricity is predominantly generated from conventional fossil fuel sources such as coal, petroleum, and natural gas. Consequently, the carbon footprint associated with EV charging may rival that of internal combustion engine (ICE) vehicles, thereby limiting the net environmental gains.

In Palestine, over 86% of the electrical supply is imported from Israel, which constitutes a critical vulnerability in the national energy framework. This dependency not only exacerbates the risk of frequent electricity shortages particularly during periods of political conflict but also contributes to elevated energy costs. In contrast, solar radiation is abundant throughout the Palestinian territories, positioning solar energy as a viable and indigenous alternative for clean, decentralized power generation.

Transitioning to solar-based EV charging infrastructure aligns with key environmental objectives, including emission reduction and progression toward net-zero carbon targets. Additionally, this shift enhances economic flexibility by decreasing external energy dependence. Given the increase cost of electricity and the volatility of supply in Palestine, the deployment of solar charging stations has become an urgent strategic imperative.

To ensure grid reliability and energy continuity, especially in remote or underserved regions, the incorporation of advanced technologies such as battery energy storage systems (BESS) and intelligent energy management platforms is essential. These systems

can stabilize power supply, optimize energy usage, and mitigate fluctuations in solar generation.

Strategic investment in renewable energy technologies supported by targeted financial incentives and robust technical infrastructure has the potential to catalyze transformative change within Palestine's energy and transportation sectors. Such initiatives would pave the way for a sustainable, resilient, and autonomous energy future.

2.2 Technical Overview and Implementations

The integration of solar photovoltaic (PV) technology into the charging infrastructure of battery electric vehicles (BEVs) presents a technically viable and environmentally sustainable solution for modern transportation systems. This is particularly relevant in regions such as Palestine, where energy insecurity and limited access to stable electricity pose significant barriers to development. A comprehensive understanding of the system's core components and implementation strategies is essential for ensuring reliable operation and long-term sustainability.

2.2.1 Technical Overview

Solar-powered BEV charging systems primarily consist of the following components: photovoltaic modules for solar energy capture, power electronics (including inverters and charge controllers), energy storage systems (typically lithium-ion battery banks), and electric vehicle supply equipment (EVSE). The direct current (DC) output from solar panels aligns efficiently with the DC charging requirements of BEVs, minimizing energy conversion losses.

However, key technical challenges must be addressed to ensure system stability and performance. The intermittency of solar irradiance introduces fluctuations in power output, which can affect both vehicles charging continuity and grid interaction. Furthermore, solar systems lack rotational or virtual inertia, which contributes to frequency instability when these systems are connected to traditional alternating current (AC) grids. These challenges necessitate the integration of advanced control strategies, including smart inverters, energy management systems (EMS), and battery energy storage systems (BESS) to buffer against variability and ensure uninterrupted power supply.

2.2.2 Implementations

In practice, solar-powered BEV charging systems can be implemented in a variety of configurations depending on site-specific factors, available resources, and intended use cases. The three primary implementation types are:

1. Grid-Tied Systems:

These systems connect to the utility grid and can export or import energy as needed. During peak solar generation, excess energy can be fed into the grid, while the grid supplements charging during periods of low solar output. Grid-tied systems benefit from net metering policies where available but require grid availability and infrastructure.

2. Off-Grid Systems:

Off-grid systems operate independently from the utility grid and rely solely on solar generation and battery storage. These are ideal for remote locations, emergency use, or regions with unreliable or absent grid infrastructure. The sizing of the PV array and battery storage must be carefully calculated to ensure uninterrupted operation.

3. Hybrid Systems:

These combine solar power with other energy sources, such as the grid or diesel generators, and often include BESS. Hybrid systems offer enhanced reliability and flexibility, making them suitable for applications where continuous operation is critical.

2.3 Technical Limitations and off-grid prospects

Several research gaps and technical limitations hinder the widespread adoption of solar-powered BEV charging stations. Key challenges include:

1. **Intermittency of Solar Energy:** The dependency on weather conditions and the lack of solar energy during nighttime necessitate the integration of energy storage systems and hybrid renewable energy sources.
2. **Grid Instability:** High penetration of solar energy into the grid can cause frequency fluctuations and power instability, requiring advanced solutions like virtual inertia devices.
3. **Space Requirements:** The installation of solar panels requires significant space, although innovations like flexible and floating solar panels are addressing this issue.
4. **Economic and Environmental Trade-offs:** While solar energy reduces carbon emissions, the manufacturing and disposal of solar panels and wind turbines present environmental challenges.

In spite of the above-mentioned limitations, off-grid stations offer a reliable solution for remote areas and where grid power is not sufficient for the new automotive technologies.

2.4 Future Prospects and Recommendations

The advancement of sustainable transportation infrastructure necessitates the integration of complementary technologies and system-level innovations to overcome existing limitations in battery electric vehicle (BEV) charging. Several future-oriented strategies offer promising enhancements to both reliability and environmental performance:

- **Hybrid Renewable Energy Systems (HRES):** The combined use of solar energy with other renewable sources such as wind or biogas can significantly enhance the consistency of power generation. This hybridization mitigates the intermittency inherent to solar-based systems and improves the overall resilience of the energy supply.
- **Battery Swapping and Fast-Charging Technologies:** To address the limitations associated with slow charging times and battery degradation, the adoption of high-speed charging infrastructure and modular battery swapping systems is essential. These approaches can reduce vehicle downtime, extend battery lifespan, and support broader BEV adoption.

- **Decentralized Energy Management:** The decentralization of energy generation and distribution facilitated by local energy networks and smart grid technologies enables improved demand-response capabilities, better load balancing, and increased system reliability. Decentralized management also enhances energy security by reducing dependency on centralized power sources.
- **Carbon-Aware Charging Strategies:** Implementing intelligent charging systems that delay or avoid vehicle charging during periods of high grid carbon intensity can substantially lower the lifecycle emissions of BEVs. Such demand-shifting strategies contribute to cleaner electricity consumption profiles and more effective integration of renewables.

In light of these considerations, the integration of solar energy into BEV charging infrastructure presents substantial potential for achieving long-term sustainability objectives and significant reductions in greenhouse gas emissions. Nevertheless, a range of technical, operational, and economic barriers must be addressed to fully realize these benefits

This need is especially critical in the context of **off-grid solar charging solutions**, which offer a viable path to electrification in remote, underserved, or energy-insecure regions. In such contexts particularly in areas afflicted by chronic energy shortages the deployment of standalone solar-powered BEV chargers equipped with energy storage systems can provide essential mobility access, reinforce energy autonomy, and promote environmental equity.

CHAPTER THREE

ANALYSIS AND DESIGN

3.1 Introduction

Solar panels are critical source of renewable energy, and the efficiency depends significantly on how they are installed. The tilt angle of solar panels, which determines their orientation relative to the sun, plays a vital role in capturing maximum solar radiation.

Figure 3. 1 Palestine Polytechnic University in Hebron

This project implements a design for an off-grid solar charging system dedicated to charging an Electric Vehicle (EV) with 12 kWh battery capacity. The system is entirely separated from the utility grid, relying entirely on solar panels to charge battery storage, which then powers an inverter capable of supplying energy to a 6 kW EV charger

Energy requirement is 12-kWh daily, this value was determined based on-site driving tests in Hebron, using a variety of electric and plug-in hybrid vehicles used by university faculty, staffs and other people. These tests provided an accurate, practical data to support the system's design and ensure it meets typical daily vehicle charging demands.

Figure 3. 2 Physical Interface of the Charging Cable with the EV at the Charging Station

3.2 Drive distance and energy consumption Analysis on test EVs / PHEVs

In this project, five electric and plug-in hybrid vehicles were analyzed to evaluate their daily energy consumption and charging requirements, with the goal of designing low power photovoltaic (PV) charging station.

1. **BMW 430e,(Dr. Mohammed Abu Taha)** a plug-in hybrid vehicle with a limited electric range of 40 km and a 12 kWh battery, relying on its combustion engine for longer trips.
2. **Hyundai Ioniq 5 (Mr. Yousef Al-Sweity)**, a fully electric vehicle with a large 58 kWh battery, demonstrated relatively high daily consumption due to its performance capabilities.
3. **Peugeot 3008 Hybrid (Ms. Noura Haroub)** showed high efficiency, often operating in electric mode for typical daily travel distances.
4. **Hyundai Kona Electric (Mr. Iyad Al-Darabi)**, designed for longer trips, features a 70 kWh battery and a range exceeding 550 km, making it well-suited for regular solar charging.

5. **Geely Geometry C (Mr. Naseem Al-Tarda)**, used commercially as a taxi, displayed stable performance and efficient energy usage.

The analysis of these vehicles helped determine an average daily consumption of approximately 6.75 kWh, forming a solid basis for designing a solar-powered charging station capable of supporting at least one vehicle per day.

- The first case is a BMW hybrid a private car that is driven on a daily basis.

The following table shows some of the vehicle specifications

Table 3.1 aims to determine the system requirements by collecting actual data from electric and hybrid vehicles over a specific period. The data was obtained through real-world use of a BMW 430e Hybrid vehicle, including parameters such as battery capacity, electric driving range, and charging durations.

By analyzing these values, the average daily energy consumption is estimated, along with the required storage capacity and configuration of the off-grid charging system. These figures form a fundamental basis for system design in terms of battery sizing and the required solar power generation to ensure adequate energy availability during daily operation.

Table 3. 1 Information table for the BMW 430e Hybrid

The information	Value
Motor capacity+ (electric motor)	2.0 CC (4-cylinder)
Battery size	12 kWh
How far the shipment is traveling	About 40 km in electric mode only
Slow charging time	About 5 hours (regular charger)
Fast shipping time	About 3.5 hours

Energy Consumption Estimation Based on Real-World BMW 430e Hybrid Readings

Table 3.1 aims to determine the energy requirements of the charging system by collecting actual daily readings from a hybrid vehicle, the BMW 430e Hybrid, over a period of 28

days. The recorded data includes daily electric energy consumption (kWh), distance traveled (km), battery charge percentage before and after trips, and odometer readings.

By analyzing this dataset, the average daily energy consumption was found to be approximately 9.31 kWh/day, while the average daily driving distance reached around 60.32 km/day. These values reflect real-world usage patterns and account for variations in driving behavior, road conditions, and battery charging levels.

The collected results serve as critical input for sizing the off-grid charging system. They enable accurate determination of the battery storage capacity and solar energy generation required to meet daily driving needs without relying on the conventional electrical grid.

Table 3. 2 Reading BMW 430 e Hybrid

Today's number	The charge consumed (kwh)	Distance traveled (Km)	Car odometer reading after charging	The percentage of the car's charge after charging	The percentage of the car's charge before shipping	Car odometer reading (Km)
1	8.4	65	135795	100	30	135730
2	9.6	80	135875	100	20	135795
3	9.48	65	135940	100	21	135875
4	10.32	69	136009	100	14	135940
5	10.2	76	136085	100	15	136009
6	10.32	40	136125	100	14	136085
7	10.2	74	136199	100	15	136125
8	7.68	75	136274	100	36	136199
9	10.2	27	136301	100	15	136274
10	7.2	77	136378	100	40	136301
11	9.48	30	136408	100	21	136378
12	10.56	78	136486	100	12	136408
13	6.6	24	136510	100	45	136486
14	8.16	77	136587	100	32	136510
15	9.48	33	136620	100	21	136587
16	9	78	136698	100	25	136620
17	7.68	57	136755	100	36	136698
18	10.32	54	136809	100	14	136755
19	9	74	136883	100	25	136809
20	10.2	25	136908	100	15	136883
21	9.96	69	136977	100	17	136908
22	9.72	36	137013	100	19	136977
23	9.84	86	137099	100	18	137013
24	9.36	68	137167	100	22	137099
25	9.96	37	137204	100	17	137167
26	10.68	72	137276	100	11	137204
27	8.64	89	137365	100	28	137276
28	8.4	54	137419	100	30	137365
	Consumption rate	Daily usage rate				
	9.308571429	60.32142857				

Both Figure 3.2 and Table 3.2 show that the amount of energy consumed per distance is not large, due to the braking system that automatically charges the vehicle battery.

Figure 3. 3 Distance Traveled vs Charge Consumed

As can be seen, the overall average energy consumption was 9.3 kWh\100km the average distance traveled was 60.32km.

- The second case is the Hyundai Ioniq hybrid a private car that is driven on a daily basis

The following table shows some of the vehicle specifications

Table 3.3 presents the technical specifications of the Hyundai Ioniq Hybrid, which was selected for analysis to estimate the energy requirements of a hybrid electric vehicle used in daily driving conditions. The primary objective of this table is to provide realistic and practical input data for designing an efficient and scalable off-grid charging system. The data includes the vehicle’s electric motor power, battery capacity, estimated driving range, and both standard and fast charging durations.

By analyzing these parameters, the required daily energy demand can be accurately determined, which in turn supports the sizing of energy storage components and the overall design of the energy supply system. With a battery capacity of 58 kW and a driving range of approximately 480 km, the Hyundai Ioniq Hybrid represents a high-efficiency use case. These values are crucial for ensuring that the proposed off-grid infrastructure can consistently meet energy demands while maintaining performance reliability and operational flexibility.

Table 3. 3 Information table for the Hyundai Ioniq Hybrid

The information	Value
Motor capacity (electric motor)	(225 hp)
Battery size	58 kWh
How far the shipment is traveling	About 480 km
Slow charging time	About 7-6 hours (standard charger)
Fast shipping time	About 1 hour (80% charge)

Energy Demand Estimation Based on Real-World Hyundai Ioniq 5 Data in Palestine

Table 3.3 presents a series of operational readings collected from the Hyundai Ioniq 5 electric vehicle during a 28-day monitoring period conducted in Palestine.

The objective of this data collection is to accurately assess the energy requirements of the charging system under real-world driving conditions within the local context. The table includes daily energy consumption in kilowatt-hours (kWh), distance traveled, battery state-of-charge before and after each trip, and odometer readings.

Analysis of the data shows that the average daily energy consumption was approximately 14.00 kWh/day, while the average daily distance traveled was around 68.93 km/day. These values reflect realistic usage patterns specific to Palestine’s environment and driving behavior, and serve as essential inputs for designing an off-grid charging system powered by renewable energy.

The results help define the required battery storage capacity and solar generation specifications to ensure continuous, efficient, and grid-independent vehicle operation.

Table 3. 4 Reading Hyundai Ioniq 5 car

Today's number	The charge consumed (kwh)	Distance traveled(km)	Car odometer reading after charging	The percentage of the car's charge after charging	The percentage of the car's charge before shipping	Car odometer reading
1	13.92	67	32194	86	62	32127
2	13.34	66	32260	83	60	32194
3	13.92	68	32328	78	54	32260
4	12.76	64	32392	87	65	32328
5	13.92	68	32460	87	63	32392
6	3.48	18	32478	84	78	32460
7	12.76	62	32540	85	63	32478
8	13.92	69	32609	90	66	32540
9	16.24	79	32688	84	56	32609
10	13.92	67	32755	84	60	32688
11	11.6	57	32812	82	62	32755
12	17.98	88	32900	86	55	32812
13	6.96	35	32935	87	75	32900
14	20.3	100	33035	84	49	32935
15	11.02	53	33088	85	66	33035
16	13.34	66	33154	91	68	33088
17	12.18	60	33214	89	68	33154
18	15.08	74	33288	78	52	33214
19	12.18	61	33349	87	66	33288
20	13.34	66	33415	88	65	33349
21	15.08	75	33490	83	57	33415
22	14.5	70	33560	84	59	33490
23	25.52	125	33685	85	41	33560
24	19.14	95	33780	90	57	33685
25	17.4	85	33865	75	45	33780
26	15.08	75	33940	90	64	33865
27	7.54	37	33977	85	72	33940
28	15.66	78	34055	84	57	33977
	Consumption rate 14.00286	Daily usage rate 68.92592593				

Both Figure 3.3 and Table 3.4 show that the amount of energy consumed per distance is not large, due to the braking system that automatically charges the vehicle battery.

Figure 3. 2 Distance Traveled vs Charge Consumed

As can be seen, the overall average energy consumption was 14 kWh\100km the average distance traveled was 68.92km.

- The third case is a Peugeot 3008 car, which belongs to a university teacher.

The following table shows some of the vehicle specifications.

Table 3.5 outlines the core technical specifications of the Peugeot 3008 Hybrid, selected as a representative vehicle for assessing the energy requirements of plug-in hybrid electric vehicles under real-world daily usage. The recorded data includes motor capacity, battery size, electric-only driving range, and both slow and fast charging durations.

The vehicle features a 13.8 kWh battery and delivers an electric-only range of approximately 55 km, making it well-suited for daily urban commuting. Charging durations vary between approximately 3 hours using a regular charger and 1.5 hours with a fast charger. These parameters serve as essential inputs for designing off-grid charging infrastructure, particularly in Palestine, where the integration of renewable energy sources is of strategic importance.

The specifications help define the required battery storage capacity and charging system configuration, ensuring reliable and efficient energy supply tailored to actual vehicle operation.

Table 3. 5 Information table for the Peugeot 3008 Hybrid

The information	Value
Motor capacity + (electric motor)	1.6cc (combined with electric motor)
Battery size	13.8 kWh
How far the shipment is traveling	About 55 km in electric mode only
Slow charging time	About 3 hours (regular charger)
Fast shipping time	About 1.5 hours

Energy Consumption Analysis Based on Real-World Operation of the Peugeot 3008 Hybrid in Palestine

Table 3.5 provides a comprehensive dataset collected from the Peugeot 3008 Hybrid over a 28-day monitoring period conducted in Palestine. The table records key operational parameters, including daily energy consumption (kWh), distance traveled (km), and the state of charge before and after driving sessions, these real-world measurements are used to accurately assess the vehicle's daily energy requirements under typical usage conditions.

Based on the collected data, the average daily energy consumption was calculated to be approximately 5.69 kWh, while the average daily driving distance reached 41.21 km. These values indicate a relatively low energy demand and moderate driving range, suggesting that the Peugeot 3008 Hybrid is a suitable candidate for integration with off-grid, solar-powered charging systems.

The data derived from this monitoring effort contributes significantly to the technical sizing of storage units, photovoltaic capacity, and energy management strategies tailored to localized operation in Palestine.

Table 3. 6 Reading Peugeot 3008 Hybrid

Today's number	The charge consumed (kwh)	Distance traveled(km)	Car odometer reading after charging	The percentage of the car's charge after charging	The percentage of the car's charge before shipping	Car odometer reading
1	3.174	23	35172	44	18	35149
2	3.726	27	35199	42	10	35172
3	3.312	24	35223	40	12	35199
4	5.658	41	35264	36	12	35223
5	13.248	96	35360	40	10	35264
6	3.036	22	35382	36	24	35360
7	9.246	67	35449	40	14	35382
8	4.416	32	35481	44	8	35449
9	3.726	27	35508	40	12	35481
10	3.312	24	35532	40	10	35508
11	3.45	25	35557	38	14	35532
12	16.284	118	35675	36	12	35557
13	4.002	29	35704	42	7	35675
14	3.588	26	35730	40	14	35704
15	10.902	79	35809	40	12	35730
16	4.278	31	35840	40	12	35809
17	7.038	51	35891	44	14	35840
18	3.864	28	35919	40	12	35891
19	5.52	40	35959	45	13	35919
20	2.208	16	35975	44	14	35959
21	5.106	37	36012	43	17	35975
22	7.452	54	36066	50	20	36012
23	6.348	46	36112	38	17	36066
24	6.072	44	36156	39	18	36112
25	7.452	54	36210	37	14	36156
26	6.21	45	36255	44	16	36210
27	5.52	40	36295	41	15	36255
28	2.07	15	36310	40	14	36295
	4.692	34	36344	44	14	36310
	Consumption rate	Daily usage rate				
	5.686551724	41.20689655				

Both Figure 3.4 and Table 3.6 show that the amount of energy consumed per distance is not large, due to the braking system that automatically charges the vehicle battery.

Figure 3. 3 Distance Traveled vs Charge Consumed

As can be seen, the overall average energy consumption was 5.68 kWh\100km the average distance traveled was 41.2 km.

- The fourth case is the Hyundai Kona Electric.

The following table shows some of the vehicle specifications

Table 3.7 outlines the core specifications of the Hyundai Kona Electric 2020, which serves as a benchmark vehicle for assessing the energy requirements of fully electric vehicles in real-world conditions.

The data includes the motor type, battery capacity, electric driving range, and both standard and fast charging durations. The vehicle features a fully electric powertrain with a battery capacity ranging from 58 to 70 kWh, depending on the model variant.

The electric range varies between 384 and 614 kilometers, reflecting a broad spectrum of usability across urban and extended-distance driving. Charging times range from 6 to 8 hours using an AC home charger to approximately 18–25 minutes with a DC fast charger (from 10% to 80%).

These specifications are critical for informing the design of off-grid, renewable energy-based charging systems, particularly in regions such as Palestine, where independent and sustainable infrastructure is essential.

The data supports accurate sizing of energy storage units and optimization of system reliability and efficiency.

Table 3. 7 Information table for the Hyundai Kona Electric 2020

Specification	The information
Motor Type	Fully electric
Battery Capacity	Approximately 58 - 70 kWh (depending on model)
Electric Range	About 384 - 614 km (depending on model and conditions)
Slow Charging Time	Around 6-8 hours (AC home charger)
Fast Charging Time	Around 18-25 minutes (DC fast charger, 10%-80%)

Energy Consumption Analysis of the Hyundai Kona Electric 2020 Based on Real-World Operation in Palestine

Table 3.7 presents a comprehensive dataset gathered from the Hyundai Kona Electric 2020 over a continuous 28-day period of daily use in Palestine. The dataset includes daily energy consumption in kilowatt-hours (kWh), distance traveled (km), battery state-of-charge before and after each trip, and odometer readings. The primary objective of this data collection is to quantify the actual energy demand of the vehicle under typical driving conditions, thereby informing the design of an off-grid, solar-powered charging system. The analysis yielded an average daily energy consumption of 13.63 kWh/day and an average daily driving distance of 82.30 km/day. These values indicate that the Hyundai Kona Electric delivers high energy efficiency with sufficient range for both urban and interurban driving. The consistent performance and energy usage make it a viable candidate for integration with standalone renewable energy systems. Such empirical data is crucial for accurately sizing battery storage capacity, determining photovoltaic generation requirements, and optimizing system autonomy—particularly in regions like Palestine, where energy resilience and sustainability are of strategic importance.

Table 3. 8 Reading Hyundai Kona Electric

Toda y's num ber	The charge consume d (kwh)	Distanc e traveled (km)	Car odometer reading after charging	The percentage of the car's charge after charging	The percentage of the car's charge before shipping	Car odometer reading
1	13.34	80	57490	90	67	57410
2	11.6	70	57560	83	63	57490
3	12.76	76	57636	85	63	57560
4	14.5	86	57722	87	62	57636
5	9.28	56	57778	87	71	57722
6	24.36	147	57925	84	42	57778
7	12.76	76	58001	85	63	57925
8	17.98	109	58110	90	59	58001
9	12.18	73	58183	84	63	58110
10	11.02	67	58250	84	65	58183
11	9.86	60	58310	82	65	58250
12	12.76	78	58388	86	64	58310
13	11.02	68	58456	87	68	58388
14	8.7	52	58508	84	69	58456
15	14.5	88	58596	85	60	58508
16	13.34	79	58675	91	68	58596
17	24.94	151	58826	95	52	58675
18	12.18	73	58899	85	64	58826
19	7.54	46	58945	87	74	58899
20	15.08	91	59036	88	62	58945
21	12.18	72	59108	83	62	59036
22	15.08	91	59199	84	58	59108
23	13.34	81	59280	85	62	59199
24	11.6	70	59350	90	70	59280
25	19.72	120	59470	80	46	59350
26	13.34	80	59550	90	67	59470
27	11.6	71	59621	85	65	59550
28	15.08	91	59712	84	58	59621
	Consump tion rate 13.63	Daily usage rate 82.2962 963				

Both Figure 3.5 and Table 3.8 show that the amount of energy consumed per distance is not large, due to the braking system that automatically charges the vehicle

Figure 3. 4 Distance Traveled vs Charge Consumed

As can be seen, the overall average energy consumption was 13.63 kWh/100km the average distance traveled was 82.29 km.

This vehicle travels long distances due to road conditions and closures in Palestine.

- The fifth case is the all-electric Chinese Geely Geometry C.

This Chinese vehicle is a taxi which is fast and completely economical and also charges automatically by braking.

The following table shows some of the vehicle specifications

Table 3.9 presents the essential specifications of the Geely Geometry C, a fully electric vehicle included in this study to assess the energy requirements of modern electric vehicles. The table provides key parameters such as motor type, battery capacity, estimated electric range, and charging durations under standard operating conditions. The vehicle is equipped with a battery ranging from 53 to 70 kWh, depending on the model variant.

The electric driving range is estimated between 400 and 550 kilometers, making the Geometry C suitable for both urban commuting and intercity travel. Charging durations range from 6 to 8 hours using an AC home charger, and 30 to 40 minutes using a DC fast charger (10%–80%). These specifications serve as critical inputs for the design of off-grid charging infrastructure powered by renewable energy. In regions like Palestine, where grid limitations and energy sustainability are major concerns, understanding such parameters is vital for optimizing battery storage sizing, photovoltaic system capacity, and overall charging system performance.

Table 3.9 Information table for the Geely Geometry C electric car

Specification	The information
Motor Type	Fully electric
Battery Capacity	Approximately 53 - 70 kWh (depending on model)
Electric Range	About 400 - 550 km (depending on model and conditions)
Slow Charging Time	Around 6-8 hours (AC home charger)
Fast Charging Time	Around 30-40 minutes (DC fast charger, 10%-80%)

Energy Consumption Assessment of the Geely Geometry C Based on Real-World Operation in Palestine

Table 3.9 presents a set of empirical data collected from the Geely Geometry C electric vehicle over a 14-day period of daily operation in Palestine. The data includes key operational parameters such as energy consumed (kWh), distance traveled (km), and battery state-of-charge before and after each trip. The aim of this data collection is to assess real-world energy consumption in order to inform the design of an efficient off-grid charging system powered by renewable energy.

The analysis of the recorded values shows an average daily energy consumption of approximately 9.54 kWh, and an average daily driving distance of about 71 km. These figures reflect moderate energy usage and range characteristics, indicating that the Geely Geometry C is suitable for daily commuting applications. Such data plays a vital role in determining the appropriate battery storage capacity, photovoltaic generation requirements, and system autonomy needed for reliable performance in renewable-powered infrastructures, particularly in regions like Palestine where energy independence is critical.

Table 3. 10 Reading Geely Geometry C electric car

Toda y's numb er	The charge consumed (kwh)	Distance traveled	Car odometer reading after charging	The percentage of the car's charge after charging	The percentage of the car's charge before shipping	Car odometer reading
1	11.66	87	6280	91	69	6193
2	3.71	30	6310	69	62	6280
3	11.66	88	6398	84	62	6310
4	7.95	59	6457	62	47	6398
5	5.83	44	6501	69	58	6457
6	5.3	39	6540	71	61	6501
7	11.66	87	6627	82	60	6540
8	11.13	82	6709	81	60	6627
9	11.66	87	6796	80	58	6709
10	11.13	82	6878	76	55	6796
11	14.84	109	6987	80	52	6878
12	10.6	80	7067	75	55	6987
13	3.18	23	7090	55	49	7067
14	13.25	97	7187	85	60	7090
	Consumptio n rate 9.54	Daily usage rate 71				

Both Figure 3.6 and Table 3.10 show that the amount of energy consumed per distance is not large, due to the braking system that automatically charges the vehicle battery.

Figure 3. 5 Distance Traveled vs Charge Consumed

As can be seen, the overall average energy consumption was 9.54 kWh\100km the average distance traveled was 71 km.

An interesting observation is the general energy consumption rate for all vehicles ranges between 9 and 14 kilowatt-hours per 100 kilometers. Since the station we are designing will charge a single vehicle, and considering the high implementation costs, we have chosen to design the station to provide **10 kwh of energy**. This decision is based on the average energy consumption rate, which is calculated to be **10.43 kwh** ensuring an efficient and cost-effective solution.

3.3 Energy Demand for Charging Batteries

Based on the gathered data from electric and hybrid cars, the need is to generate 10 KW of energy. To calculate the power required to charge the batteries over a specific time period:

$$P_{\text{Required}} = \frac{E_{\text{Battery}}}{\Delta t} \tag{3.1}$$

Explanation:

This formula calculates the average power required to charge a battery.

Symbols:

P_{required} : Average power required (kW).

E_{battery} : Energy stored in the battery (kWh).

Δt : Charging duration (hours).

Substituting values:

Required Power = 10 kW

Loss Percentage = 30%

$P_{\text{Required}} = (10 + (6 * 0.3)) = 11.8 \text{KW}$

Solar Panel Sizing

To account for system inefficiencies and calculate the total energy required from solar panels:

$$E_{\text{Battery}} = \frac{E_{\text{Battery}}}{\eta} \quad (3.2)$$

Explanation:

This formula accounts for system losses to estimate the total energy demand.

Symbols:

E_{solar} : Energy required from the solar panels (kWh).

E_{Battery} : Energy stored in the battery (kWh).

η : Efficiency of the battery = **85%**.

Substituting values:

$E_{\text{solar}} = 10 / 0.85 \approx 11.3 \text{kWh}$.

To calculate the number of panels required to meet this energy demand:

$$N_{\text{panels}} = \frac{E_{\text{solar}}}{(P_{\text{panel}} \times G)} \quad (3.3)$$

Explanation:

This formula estimates the number of solar panels required based on their power rating and sunlight availability.

Symbols:

N_{panels} : Number of solar panels.

E_{solar} : Total energy required from solar panels (kWh).

P_{tile} : Power output of a single panel (kW). G : Average sunlight duration per day (hours).

$P_{\text{panel}} = 610 \text{W}$

Table 3. 11 Number of hours of sunshine per month in the cities of Hebron, Nablus, and Jericho

Month	Hebron	Nablus	Jericho
January	4.7	4.5	5.5
February	4.8	4.8	5.9
March	6.4	6.4	7.7
April	8.1	8.2	9.3
May	9.0	8.9	9.4
June	8.3	8.4	11.8
July	9.6	9.6	11.7
August	10.9	10.9	11.6
September	10.3	10.2	10.5
October	9.8	9.8	8.7
November	7.0	7.0	6.5
December	4.7	4.7	5.6

the peak sun hours average 7.8 hours per day. In contrast, during the winter, peak sun hours are reduced to approximately half or even less, with some days experiencing no peak sun hours at all.

According to previous studies the sun's peak hour in Palestine is 5.9 h to be suitable for summer and winter

Substituting values:

$N_{\text{panels}} = 11.3 / (0.6 \times 3.9) = 5.2$ panels. So, the number of panels we need to provide 11.3 kilowatts is ≈ 6 panels.

Panels in Series

In a series connection, the **voltage adds up** while the current remains constant.

Voltage of one panel: $V_{\text{panel}} = 40 \text{ V}$

System voltage required: $V_{\text{system}} = 48 \text{ V}$

$N_{\text{series}} = 6$ panels in series

Battery Storage Sizing

The capacity of the battery storage system can be calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Capacity}_{(\text{Ah})} = \frac{(E_{\text{storage}} * 1000)}{V_{\text{battery}}} \quad (3.4)$$

Explanation:

This formula converts the energy demand into the required battery capacity in ampere-hours.

Symbols:

Capacity: Battery capacity (Ah).

E_{storage} : Energy required for storage (kWh).

V_{battery} : Voltage of the battery system (V). Substituting values:

$$\text{Capacity (Ah)} = (11.3 \times 1000) / 48 \approx 235\text{Ah}.$$

If each battery has a capacity of 300 Ah, the number of batteries required can be calculated as:

$$N_{\text{batteries}} = \frac{\text{Capacity}}{\text{Capacity_per_battery}} \quad (3.5)$$

Substituting values:

$$N_{\text{batteries}} = 500 / 300 \approx 2 \text{ batteries}.$$

Inverter Sizing

The inverter must handle the full power of the charger:

$$P_{\text{inverter}} = P_{\text{charger}} \quad (3.6)$$

Explanation:

This formula ensures that the inverter is sized to match the maximum power required by the charger.

Symbols:

P_{inverter} : Inverter power capacity (kW).

P_{charger} : Charger power requirement (kW). Substituting values:

$P_{\text{inverter}} = 6 \text{ kW}$. Adding a safety margin

How the Safety Margin is Applied

The car charger requires **6 kW** of power.

A safety margin of **10%** is typically applied:

$$P_{\text{inverter}} = P_{\text{charger}} \times (1 + \text{Safety Margin}). P_{\text{inverter}} = 6\text{kW} \times 1.1 = 6.6\text{KW} \approx 6\text{KW}$$

3.10 Declination Angle (δ)

Is the angle between the equatorial plane and the line that connects between the earth's center and the sun's center. The declination angle varies seasonally between 23.45 and -23.45 and is calculated from the following relationship.

The formula is:

$$\delta = -23.45 \times \cos\left(\frac{360}{365} \times (n + 10.5)\right)$$

The Earth is tilted at an angle of **23.45°**. This tilt causes the sun to appear north or south of the equator at different times of the year.

The cos function accounts for the cyclical nature of the Earth's orbit around the sun.

The **factor** $\frac{360}{365}$ translates the day of the year (n) into an angular position as the Earth moves around the sun.

n = the day number, such that n = 1 on the 1st of January.

+10.5: This adjusts the calculation to account for small shifts in the Earth's orbit relative to the calendar.

Outcome (δ): The declination angle helps determine how high the sun will appear in the sky on any given day of the year.

The altitude angle (α): is the angle between the horizontal and the rays of the sun. Therefore, the altitude angle for sunrise and sunset equals zero. The altitude angle (α) is calculated by:

$$\sin \alpha = \sin \delta \sin \phi + \cos \delta \cos \phi \cos h$$

The hour angles at sunrise and sunset (h_s) have the same magnitude and can be calculated by substituting $\alpha = 0$ into the previous equation (Equation (2)) to obtain:

$$h_s = \cos^{-1}[-\tan^{-1} \phi \tan \delta]$$

3.11 The tilt angle (β)

Is the angle between the horizontal and the tilted surface.

The total solar radiation is the sum of the direct, diffuse, and reflected solar radiation. Firstly, direct radiation depends on the atmosphere's thickness, the quantity of water vapor, and the level of pollution in the atmosphere. Secondly, diffuse solar radiation is defined as all the solar radiation that comes from the sky except for the part that comes directly from the sun. Therefore, it is difficult to calculate because it totally depends on highly variable cloudiness and atmospheric clarity. Finally, reflected radiation from buildings, cars, the ground, and streets must be calculated individually. For that reason, reflected radiation is usually neglected.

$$I_d = \frac{24}{\pi} I_m [1 + 0.034 \cos(\frac{2\pi n}{365})] \times [\cos(\phi - \beta) \cos(\delta) \sin(h_s) + h_s \sin(\phi - \beta) \sin(\delta)] \quad (4)$$

From Equation (4), for a particular day n to have an optimum tilt angle ($\beta_{opt, d}$), the total radiation I_d must be derived with respect to the tilt angle (β) and equalized with the resulting derivative set to zero, i.e., $\frac{dI_d}{d\beta} = 0.0$. to obtain:

$$\beta_{opt, m} = \phi - \tan^{-1}[\frac{h_s}{\sin(h_s)} \times \tan(\delta)]$$

The term $\frac{24}{\pi}$: Converts the daily solar radiation into an average value.

I_m : The solar radiation outside Earth's atmosphere, which is roughly **1367 W/m²**.

The factor $1+0.034\times\cos\left(\frac{2\pi n}{365}\right)$: Adjusts for the varying distance between Earth and the sun throughout the year.

ϕ : The latitude of the location, which determines the sun's angle relative to the ground.
(31.5°for Hebron)

β : The tilt angle of the solar panel.

δ : The declination angle, calculated in Step 1.

h_s : The hour angle at sunset, which shows how far the sun is from the highest point in the sky.

The value I_m represents the extraterrestrial solar radiation, which is the theoretical amount of sunlight that reaches the Earth's surface if there were no atmosphere. In January, this value is relatively high due to astronomical calculations based on the Earth's position relative to the sun and the angle of the sun's tilt (being lower in the sky). This makes I_m appear higher in January compared to February and March.

However, the actual solar radiation that reaches the Earth's surface and affects solar panels (known as **GHI**) does not follow the same trend. While I_m may be higher in January, the actual radiation is typically lower compared to February and March. This is because the sun is positioned lower in the sky during January, which increases the atmospheric path that sunlight has to travel through. As a result, more radiation is absorbed or scattered by the atmosphere. Additionally, heavy winter clouds often reduce direct sunlight, and the shorter daylight hours in January limit the total amount of radiation available.

In contrast, during February and March, the sun is higher in the sky, and daylight hours are longer, which increases the actual solar radiation reaching solar panels, even if the theoretical value I_m is slightly lower during these months.

I_m does not directly indicate the actual solar radiation falling on solar panels. Instead, it provides a theoretical benchmark, while the actual radiation depends on atmospheric conditions, daylight duration, and the sun's position in the sky.

The optimal tilt angle is crucial because it directly affects the amount of solar energy that the PV panels can capture. By adjusting the tilt angle according to the sun's position, which changes with the seasons and time of day, the panels can operate at peak efficiency. This optimization leads to higher energy production, better economic returns, and more effective use of solar energy resources

Figure 3. 6 Solar angles in tracking sun position

Table 3. 12 The monthly optimum tilt angle β_{optima} and extraterrestrial radiation I_m in kWh/m² for the main

Month		City								
		Rafah	Gaza	Hebron	Jericho	Jerusalem	Ramallah	Nablus	Tulkarm	Jenin
January	β_{optima}	58.85	59.06	59.06	59.36	59.28	59.39	59.67	59.75	59.89
	I_m	342.67	342.4	342.4	342.01	342.11	341.97	341.6	341.5	341.32
February	β_{optima}	49.98	50.2	50.2	50.52	50.44	50.55	50.85	50.94	51.08
	I_m	303.99	303.9	303.9	303.78	303.81	303.77	303.65	303.61	303.55
March	β_{optima}	34.72	34.96	34.96	35.3	35.21	35.33	35.65	35.74	35.89
	I_m	314.6	314.62	314.62	314.64	314.63	314.64	314.66	314.65	314.66
April	β_{optima}	15.34	15.57	15.57	15.89	15.81	15.92	16.23	16.31	16.46
	I_m	316.32	316.31	316.31	316.28	316.29	316.28	316.25	316.25	316.24
May	β_{optima}	-0.62	-0.42	-0.42	-0.14	-0.21	-0.11	0.15	0.23	0.35
	I_m	344.44	344.44	344.44	344.44	344.44	344.44	344.44	344.44	344.44
I_m (negative values of β_{optima} are considered zero)		344.42	344.43	344.43	344.44	344.44	344.44	344.44	344.44	344.44
June	β_{optima}	-7.68	-7.50	-7.50	-7.24	-7.31	-7.22	-6.98	-6.91	-6.80
	I_m	346.44	346.49	346.49	346.55	346.53	346.56	346.62	346.63	346.66
I_m (negative values of β_{optima} are considered zero)		343.33	343.52	343.52	343.79	343.72	343.81	344.05	344.11	344.22
July	β_{optima}	-4.33	-4.14	-4.14	-3.87	-3.94	-3.84	-3.59	-3.52	-3.40
	I_m	349.37	349.39	349.39	349.42	349.41	349.42	349.45	349.45	349.47
I_m (negative values of β_{optima} are considered zero)		348.37	348.48	348.48	348.62	348.58	348.63	348.76	348.8	348.85
August	β_{optima}	9.08	9.3	9.3	9.61	9.53	9.64	9.93	10.01	10.15
	I_m	328.32	328.3	328.3	328.27	328.28	328.27	328.24	328.23	328.22
September	β_{optima}	28.18	28.41	28.41	28.75	28.66	28.78	29.1	29.19	29.34
	I_m	320.28	320.28	320.28	320.27	320.27	320.27	320.27	320.26	320.26
October	β_{optima}	45.68	45.91	45.91	46.23	46.15	46.26	46.57	46.66	46.8

Month	City									
	Im	329.42	329.37	329.37	329.29	329.31	329.28	329.21	329.19	329.15
November	β_{optima}	56.97	57.18	57.18	57.49	57.41	57.52	57.8	57.89	58.02
	Im	328.45	328.23	328.23	327.93	328.01	327.9	327.61	327.52	327.39
December	β_{optima}	61.32	61.53	61.53	61.82	61.74	61.85	62.13	62.2	62.33
	Im	342.95	342.6	342.6	342.11	342.24	342.07	341.6	341.46	341.24
	Total	3967.24	3966.32	3966.32	3964.99	3965.34	3964.86	3963.58	3963.21	3962.59
Total (negative values of β_{optima} are considered zero)		3963.12	3962.44	3962.44	3961.43	3961.69	3961.33	3960.33	3960.03	3959.54

Figure 3. 7 The monthly optimum tilt angle β_{optima} for Hebron, Nablus, and Jericho

The Figure above illustrates the monthly optimal tilt angles (β_{optima}) required for solar panels in Hebron, Nablus, and Jericho. These angles are adjusted to maximize solar energy absorption by aligning the panels with the sun's position throughout the year. The chart highlights a noticeable variation in angles, with higher values during winter months when the sun is lower in the sky and lower values during summer when the sun is higher the optimal angle varies monthly due to the changing position of the sun (elevation and declination).

Higher angles are required in winter (December, January) due to the sun's low position in the sky.

Lower angles are suitable in summer (May - July) due to the sun's high position.

Calculating the Annual Average Optimal Angle in Hebron:

$$Average\ Optimal\ Angel = \sum_{n=1}^{12} (\beta_{optima}) / 12$$

$$\Sigma\beta_{optima} = 59.06 + 50.20 + 34.96 + 15.57 + 0.00 + 0.00 + 0.00 + 9.30 + 28.41 + 45.91 + 57.18 + 61.53$$

$$\Sigma\beta_{optima} = 362.12^\circ$$

$$\text{Average Optimal Angle} = \frac{362.12^\circ}{12} = 30.17^\circ$$

The optimal angle is 30.17° for a fixed system.

Energy Production (P)=System Efficiency (η) \times Solar Radiation Intensity (I) \times Total Panel Area (A)

Where:

P: Energy produced (in watts or kilowatt-hours, kWh).

η : Efficiency of the solar system (percentage, converted to decimal).

I: Solar radiation intensity (kWh/m²).

A: Total effective panel area (m²).

3.4 Monthly Energy Production Estimation

Parameters :

Panel area per unit (A₁) = 2.591 m²

Number of panels (n) = 6

Total area (A) = 2.591 \times 6=15.546 m²

Efficiency (η) = 18%

Monthly Energy Production = $\eta \times I \times A$ (3.12) Hebron in January

I = 342.4 kWh/m²

H = 0.18

A = 15.546 m²

Energy Production=0.18 \times 342.4 \times 15.546= 958.13 kWh

Stable 3. 13 Monthly Energy Production

Month	Im Solar Radiation (kWh/m ²)	Energy Production (kWh)
January	342.40	958.13
February	303.90	850.40
March	314.62	880.39
April	316.31	885.12
May	344.44	963.84
June	346.49	969.58
July	349.39	977.69
August	328.30	918.68
September	320.28	896.23
October	329.37	921.67
November	328.23	918.48
December	342.60	958.69

The average energy produced by optimizing the tilt angle throughout the year amounts to 924.91 kWh, reflecting the system's efficiency in adapting to seasonal variations in solar radiation.

The fixed tilt angle of 30.17° falls between 28.41° and 34.96°. This positioning aligns the solar panels to effectively capture solar radiation, maximizing energy production by leveraging an optimal balance between these angles.

And I found through the interpolation work that the amount of energy produced at the fixed angle is 884.65kWh

Δ Energy = Energy at Optimized Angle – Energy at Fixed Angle

Δ Energy = 924.91 – 884.65=40.26kWh

$$\frac{\Delta \text{Energy}}{\text{Energy at fixed Angle}} * 100\% = \frac{40.26}{884.65} \approx 4.55\%$$

The regions with latitudes between 0° and 30°, it might be beneficial to design solar panels with moving tilt angles. However, in Palestinian cities, moving tilt angles are unnecessary. Adjusting solar panels yearly, semi-annually, seasonally, or monthly can significantly improve energy output compared to a fixed horizontal surface. Monthly adjustments provide the highest increase, generating approximately 17% more energy, while semi-annual adjustments yield around 15% more energy, the latter option is the better cost-efficient one.

In comparison to a fixed annual tilt angle, monthly adjustments can enhance energy generation by approximately 6%, whereas semi-annual adjustments yield an increase of around 5%. These results highlight the benefit of periodic tilt optimization, with semi-annual adjustments offering a practical and efficient solution for rooftop photovoltaic systems.

The daily tilt angle for Palestinian cities ranges from -8° in June to 62° in December. Monthly tilt angles vary between -7° in June and 62° in December, while seasonal tilt angles range from -1° in June to 58° in December. The semi-annual tilt angles are typically 7° during the warm months (April to September) and 52° during the cold months (October to March). These variations demonstrate how the optimal tilt angle shifts throughout the year to capture the sun's changing position effectively.

The yearly optimum tilt angle for most Palestinian cities is approximately 30°. It also notes that the monthly optimal tilt angle for any month closely aligns with the average of

the daily angles during that month, while seasonal and yearly optimal tilt angles correspond to the average monthly angles for their respective periods.

We observe that the ratio between the dynamic system and the static system is quite small, making the static system the more practical choice. This is because dynamic systems are typically more expensive and their benefits are negligible unless implemented in large-scale projects or for individuals who are less concerned about the cost.

Compared to a horizontal surface, yearly, semi-annual, seasonal, and monthly adjustments of solar panels in the main Palestinian cities will generate approximately 10%, 15%, 15%, and 17% more energy, respectively, whereas compared to the fixed optimum yearly tilt angle, monthly adjustments of the solar panels in the main Palestinian cities can generate about 6% more energy. Seasonal and semi-annual adjustments can generate about 5% more solar energy.

Since the amount of energy generated from the dynamic solar radiation system is small for the system to be installed and since its cost is high as we are students, the best option is to build a system with a fixed angle.

In Hebron, the average daily sunshine duration throughout the entire year was **7.8 hours**, based on the recorded data from the Palestinian Meteorological Department.

Figure 3. 8 monthly, Energy Production, Solar Radiation

The Figure illustrates the relationship between months, the optimal tilt angle, and solar radiation. During the winter months, the sun is closer to the Earth, necessitating a larger tilt angle for solar panels to maximize the capture of solar radiation. Conversely, during

the summer months, the sun is more directly overhead, requiring a smaller tilt angle, which can even approach zero in certain months.

It is also evident that the amount of solar radiation varies between seasons due to the changing position of the sun. For instance, in some winter months, the solar radiation levels are higher. This is because the radiation values depicted in the table represent extraterrestrial radiation (outside the Earth's atmosphere). When this radiation penetrates the atmosphere, it diminishes, resulting in lower levels compared to the summer months. Therefore, determining the optimal tilt angle for solar panels is crucial to ensure consistent energy capture throughout the year. This optimization enhances the efficiency of solar panels and maximizes energy production, addressing seasonal variations in solar radiation.

Angle 30 was the best angle to get the same solar radiation and amount of energy we need throughout the year.

CHAPTER FOUR

STRUCTURAL DESIGN

4.1 Introduction:

With the rapid development in the transportation and energy sectors, integrating renewable energy technologies with electric transportation has become a strategic option to combat climate change and reduce dependence on fossil fuels. In this context, the aim of this project is to design a solar-powered charging station dedicated to electric and plug-in hybrid vehicles (EV/PHEV), with a focus on the structural design of the canopy that will support the solar panels and provide shelter for vehicles.

The design will involve constructing a structural canopy composed of steel columns and beams (such as Square Hollow Sections—SHS—and IPE beams), taking into account the various loads that may act on the structure. These include:

- **Dead Load:** This includes the self-weight of the structure and the solar panels.
- **Live Load:** Such as the weight of technicians during maintenance or temporary objects.
- **Wind Load:** Horizontal forces acting on the structure, especially in open areas.

4.2 Structure Design

Figure 4. 1 Site Front/Side View

The Figure 4.1 above shows the dimensions of the work site where the solar Pannels would be installed.

Structure Dimensions:

Width of the structure: 4.00 m.

Length of the structure: 5.00 m.

Yield Strength (YS): $235 \text{ MPa} = 235 \times 10^6 \text{ pa}$ (steel structure)

Total height: $h = 2.80 + 1.20 = 4.00 \text{ m}$

4.2.1 General Structure Design:

- Structural Configuration

The structural frame supporting the photovoltaic (PV) modules was designed in accordance with the site's geometric constraints and anticipated environmental loads. As depicted in Figure 4.1, the system comprises vertical steel columns and inclined steel beams, configured to position the solar panels at a tilt angle of approximately 30° , which is considered optimal for maximizing annual solar energy capture.

The total height of the structure is 4.00 meters, consisting of a 2.80-meter vertical column and an additional 1.20 meters arising from the sloped configuration of the inclined beam.

- Materials Specification

The structure is constructed primarily from structural steel with a yield strength of 235 MPa, providing high resistance to mechanical stresses and ensuring structural integrity under various load conditions. This material was selected due to its favorable mechanical properties, durability, and suitability for bolted assembly.

- Applied Loads

The structural system was analyzed under the following load categories:

1. Dead Loads

These include the self-weight of the steel framework and the solar panels.

2. Wind Loads

Calculated based on ASCE 7-10 (2013) guidelines, with a design wind speed of 30.5 m/s. Wind induces:

- Drag Force: Acts horizontally along the surface area of the solar panels.
- Lift Force: Acts vertically, generated by wind interaction with the inclined surfaces.

3. Live Loads

Include transient forces such as the weight of maintenance personnel and servicing equipment.

4. Snow Loads

In locations where snowfall is expected, snow accumulation must be considered. Snow load densities are typically assumed in the range of 0.2 to 0.5 kN/m². These loads were incorporated into the design to ensure safety and reliability under winter conditions.

- Construction and Assembly

The structural elements are as follows:

- Inclined Beams: Constructed using IPE 200 steel sections.
- Vertical Columns: Made from SHS 200/5 square hollow sections.

These components were selected based on structural analysis verifying their resistance to axial forces and susceptibility to buckling. All joints are to be bolted, facilitating modularity, ease of assembly, and future disassembly. The entire frame is anchored securely to reinforced concrete foundations to ensure stability against both vertical and lateral loads.

- Sustainability and Future Development

The design prioritizes mechanical stability and long-term structural performance, while also allowing for future system upgrades or expansions. Furthermore, it is compatible with geotechnical assessments and advanced structural analysis software, enabling accurate modeling under diverse environmental loading scenarios. The material selection and modular approach contribute to the system's overall sustainability and adaptability.

4.3 Wind Load

The Wind load depends on several factors; each has its own calculations shown in the detailed sections below.

4.3.1 Calculate Wind Speed at Installation Height($v(z)$)

$$v(z) = v(z_0) * \left(\frac{z}{z_0}\right)^\alpha$$

Eq. 4. 1 Wind Speed

Where:

$v(z_0) = 35\text{m/s}$ (wind speed at reference in Palestine)

$z_0 = 10\text{m}$ (reference height in Palestine),

$z = 4\text{m}$ (installation height in Palestine),

$\alpha = 0.15$ (height factor for open terrain in Palestine)

$$v(z) = 35 * \left(\frac{4}{10}\right)^{0.15}$$

$$v(z) = \frac{30.5\text{m}}{\text{s}}$$

4.3.2 Panel Area (A)

Using rectangular shapes area for panel according to the following equation:

$$A_{\text{panel}} = \text{Length} \times \text{Width}$$

Eq. 4. 2 Panel Area

Panel Dimensions:

Length = 2.285m

Width = 1.134m

The hypotenuse represents the length of the panel.

$$A_{\text{drag}} = A_{\text{ORGENAL}} * \sin\theta$$

Eq. 4. 3 Drag Area

$$A_{\text{lift}} = A_{\text{ORGENAL}} * \cos\theta$$

Eq. 4. 4 Lift Area

$$A_{\text{drag}} = 2.59 * \sin 30 = 1.3 \text{ m}^2$$

$$A_{lift} = 2.59 * \cos 30 = 2.24 \text{ m}^2$$

4.3.3 Calculate Dynamic Wind Pressure (qb)

$$\text{Wind Speed (v): } \frac{30.5\text{m}}{\text{s}}$$

$$\text{Air Density (} \rho \text{) : } 1.225 \text{ kg/m}^3$$

$$qb = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \rho \cdot v^2$$

Eq. 4. 5 Wind Pressure

$$qb = 569.7 \frac{\text{N}^2}{\text{m}}$$

4.3.4 Calculate Drag Force (**Fd**)

$$Fd = Pd \cdot A \cdot Cd$$

Eq. 4. 6 Drag Force

$$\text{Area (A): } 1.3 \text{ m}^2$$

$$\text{Drag Coefficient (} C_d \text{) : } 1$$

$$Fd = 569.7 * 1.3 * 1 = 740.61\text{N}$$

Calculate total Drag Force (**F**)

$$F_{total} = 6 * 740.61 = 4443.6\text{N}$$

4.3.5 Calculate Lift Force (F_l)

$$Fl = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \rho \cdot v^2 \cdot C_l \cdot A$$

Eq. 4. 7 Lift Force

$$Fl = 0.6125 * 30.5^2 * 0.17 * 2.24 = 216.97\text{N}$$

Calculate total Lift Force (F_l):

$$F_{total\ lift} = 6 * 216.97 = 1301.82N$$

4.3.6 Total wind force (total)

$$F_{total} = \sqrt{F_d^2 + (F_l - w_{ld})^2}$$

Eq. 4. 8 Total wind load

$$\text{total Drag Force } (F_d) = 4443.6N$$

$$\text{total Lift Force } (F_l) = 1301.82N$$

$$W_{total} = 1765.8N$$

$$F_{total} = \sqrt{4443.6^2 + 1301.82^2} = 4630.36N$$

$$\mathbf{F_{total} = 4630.3N = 4.63 KN}$$

4.4 Dead Load (D)

General formula for dead load

$$W = m \cdot g$$

4.4.1 Panel dead load

Panel mass (m): 30 kg

Gravitational acceleration (g): 9.81 m/s

Number of panels: 6

Dead load per panel

$$D_{panel} = 30 \cdot 9.81 = 294.3N$$

4.4.2 Beams load (assuming we use PEI 160)

Beam length = $5 \times 2 + 4 \times 2 = 18$ m, Beam mass per meter = 6 Kg/m

Total Beam mass = $15.5 * 18 = 279$ Kg

Total Beam weight = $279 * 9.81 = 2737$ N

4.4.3 Total dead load

Dead load = all panels load + Beams load

All panels load = $294.3 * 6 = 1765.8$ N

Total dead load = total beam weight + total panel weight = $2737 + 1766 = 4503$ N

Total Dead Load = 4503 N = 4.5 KN

4.5 Live load

The Calculation of Live load depends on the structural use, therefore each structure has its own assumption to calculate the live load, these assumptions and calculations are listed in the following sections.

4.5.1 Assumption of live load

Since the structure is a roof and the live load on the roof will be a maintenance load only to clean the solar panels when needed by 1 adult man, and the average weight of an adult man is 90 Kg.

4.5.2 Calculation of the live load

Live load = $90 * 9.81 = 882.9$ N = 0.88 KN

4.6 Snow load

4.6.1 Data collection and equations

After looking into Jordanian Structural design code, we found the snow load depends on Mean Sea Level (MSL) of the project site, and according to figure (4.2) below, we find

the MSL of our project is between (880m – 900m) , we select the upper limit 900 m to be in the safe side.

Figure 4. Mean sea level of project site

The Table (4.1) show the snow load vs MSL, according to Jordanian Code :

Table 4. 1 snow load vs MSL

1	$h < 250$	0
2	$500 > h > 250$	$(h-250)/1000$
3	$1500 > h > 500$	$(h-400)/400$
4	$2500 > h > 1500$	$(h-812.5)/250$

4.6.2 Snow load Calculations

Our site MSL = 900, which is the 3rd category in table ().

$$SL = (h-400)/400 = (900-400)/400 = 500/400 = 1.25 \text{ KN/m}^2.$$

$$\text{Project area} = 4 \times 5 = 20 \text{ m}^2$$

$$\text{Snow load for our project} = 1.25 * 20 = 25 \text{ KN}$$

4.7 Load combination

D (dead load) = 4.03 KN

E_r (live load roof) = 0.88 KN

W (wind load) = 4.5 KN

S (snow load) = 25 KN

To calculate Total load according to (ASCE, 2013)

$$F_t = 1.2 D + 1.6 W + E + 0.5 (E_r \text{ or } S)$$

Eq. 4. 9 Load Combination

Where:

F_t is Total load.

D is Dead load

W is wind load

E is live load

E_r is live load roof

S is snow load

Therefore, the total load is:

$$F_t = 1.2 * 4.5 + 1.6 * 4.5 + 0.88 + 0.5*25$$

$$F_t = 5.4 + 7.2 + 0.88 + 12.5$$

$$\underline{\underline{F_t = 25.98 \text{ KN} \approx 26 \text{ KN}}}$$

4.8 Column Design:

4.8.1 Axial Load design (compression)

Steel is high compression resistant material, and normally we don't design columns on compression, but the section selection depends on Buckling force, as for compression on our column, it's the load stress calculated by stress formula

$$C_s = F/A$$

Eq. 4. 10 Compression Stress

Where:

C_s: Compression Stress on column.

F: force applied on column.

Since column is a support for the structure then the force applied on our columns equal $F = Ft/4$ (we used 4 columns in our project to support the structure).

A: Area of the section, its value found in design tables.

4.8.2 Compression Calculations for SHS

Figure 4. 3 Beam Distribution (plan view)

The Square Hollow Section (SHS) we chose for our project is (SHS 200/5).

the total vertical load is equally distributed among 4 columns:

$$F_{axial} = \frac{F_{total}}{4}$$

$$F_{axial} = \frac{26}{4} = 6.5 \text{ KN}$$

Stress on column (compression) = $F/A = 6.5 \times 10^3 \text{ (N)} / 3873 \text{ (mm}^2\text{)} = 1.67 \text{ MPa}$

Since stress on column = $1.67 \text{ MPa} < \text{Steel yield strength} = 235 \text{ MPa}$

Then Square Hollow Sections SHS (200/5) is safe to use in our structure.

4.8.3 Compression Calculations for I-Beam

The I-Beam section (IPE) we chose for our project is (IPE 200).

Stress on column (compression) = $F/A = 6.5 \times 10^3 \text{ (N)} / 2848 \text{ (mm}^2\text{)} = 2.28 \text{ MPa}$

Since stress on column = $2.28 \text{ MPa} < \text{Steel yield strength} = 235 \text{ MPa}$

Then I-Beam Section IPE 200 is safe to use in our structure

4.9 Buckling design for column

Buckling design follow Euler general formula (McCORMAC & CSERNAK, 2017), shown below:

$$P_{critical} = \frac{E * I * (\pi)^2}{(Sr * L)^2}$$

Eq. 4. 11 Euler General Formula

Where:

E: modulus of elasticity

I: second moment of area, known as moment of Inertia, we find its value in the design tables.

Sr: Slender ratio, see thorough explanation below:

When Buckling happens in column, it depends on the slender ratio of the column, what we mean by slender ratio is a numerical description of how much the column is thin in comparison to its length, and the columns has 3 classes of slenderness:

- 1- Long columns, when slender ratio is more than 150
- 2- Intermediate columns, when slender ratio is between 40 and 150
- 3- Short columns, when slender ratio is less than 40

slender Ratio formula is:

$$Sr = KL/r$$

Eq. 4. 12 Slender Ratio Formula

L = laterally unbraced length of the member (the same as Length since embraced length is negligible)

r = radius of gyration we find its values in the design tables.

K = Effective length factor calculates from table (4.4) below

Effective length factor K for axially loaded columns with various end conditions						
Buckled shape of column is shown by dashed line	(a)	(b)	(c)	(d)	(e)	(f)
Theoretical K Value	0.5	0.7	1.0	1.0	2.0	2.0
Recommended design value when ideal condition are approximated	0.65	0.80	1.2	1.0	2.10	2.0
End Condition code						

Figure 4.4 Effective Length Factor (K))

K for our project is 0.7 since we have partially fixed column, since the foundation of beam is fixed, and we will design the beam connection the column with bolts, and bolts connection is pin support, see case (b) in table (4.4) above.

4.10.1 Buckling Calculations for SHS

Since we select SHS 200/5 and its values are shown below:

$$E = \text{Modulus of Elasticity of steel} = 210 \times 10^3 \text{ MPa} = 210 \times 10^3 \text{ N/mm}^2$$

$$I = \text{moment of inertia of Square Hollow Sections SHS (200/5)} = 24.45 \times 10^6 \text{ mm}^4$$

$$S_r = \text{slenderness ratio} = KL/r = 0.7 * 3000 / 79.5 = 26.4 \text{ (short column } 26 < 40)$$

$$P_{\text{critical}} = (210 \times 10^3 \times 24.45 \times 10^6 \times 3.14^2) / (79.5 * 3000)^2 = 8069.6 \text{ N}$$

$$F_{\text{axial}} < P_{\text{critical}} \text{ to be safe}$$

$$6500 \text{ N} < 8069.6 \text{ N} \text{ (design is safe)}$$

Then Square Hollow Sections (SHS 200 / 5) is safe to use in our structure with a wight of 30.4 kg/m.

4.10.2 Buckling Calculations for IPE

Since we select IPE 200 and its values are shown below:

$$E = \text{Modulus of Elasticity of steel} = 210 \times 10^3 \text{ MPa} = 210 \times 10^3 \text{ N/mm}^2$$

$$I = \text{moment of inertia of I-Beam Section IPE 200} = 19.43 \times 10^6 \text{ mm}^4$$

$$S_r = \text{slenderness ratio} = KL/r = 0.7 * 3000 / 82.6 = 25.4 \text{ (short column } 25 < 40)$$

$$P_{\text{critical}} = (210 \times 10^3 \times 19.43 \times 10^6 \times 3.14^2) / (82.6 * 3000)^2 = 6922.6 \text{ N}$$

$$F_{\text{axial}} < P_{\text{critical}} \text{ to be safe}$$

$$6500 \text{ N} < 6922 \text{ N} \text{ (design is safe)}$$

Then I-beam sections IPE 200 is safe to use in our structure with a wight of 22.4 Kg/m.

Design Recommendation:

We Recommend the use of I-beam section IPE200 in this project, since it fulfill the duty and has lower cost/weight than SHS section.

4.11 Beam Design

We have slab design for an Area of 4m X 5 m, this is square like and has 2-way load distribution, to make the slab 1-way load distribution slab we split the area into 3 sections, each one with dimension of (400 CM X 167 CM), with 4 Main beams named (B1&B2) and 2 secondary beams (graders) named (G1), like shown in the figure (4.5) below:

Figure 4. 5 Beam Distribution (plan view)

4.12 Load Distribution on Beams

Figure 4. 7 Beam B1 Load & analysis

The maximum bending moment for a simply supported beam according to (Hibbeler, 2016) is:

$$M = \frac{w * l^2}{8}$$

Eq. 4. 13 Simple Supported Beam Maximum Binding Moment

$$M = \frac{1.08 * 4^2}{8} = 2.16Kn.m$$

And from design tables we can select the proper section for our project, either I-beam or SHS:

- 1- **I-Beam design:** we select IPE80 with elastic binding moment resistance of 4.71 KN.m > 2.16 KN.m, therefore IPE80 is safe for B1 beams, with weight =6 Kg/m.
- 2- **SHS design:** we select SHS 50/4 with elastic binding moment resistance of 2.35 KN.m > 2.16 KN.m, therefore SHS 50/4 is safe for B1 Beams, with weight=5.64Kg/m

4.13.2 Design for Beam B2

The beam B2 is connected to Graders (G1) from each end with welding, and weld connections are Fixed supports.

Since Weld doesn't allow rotation, therefore we have a Fixed ended supported beam named (B2) with load W as shown in figure 4.6 below:

Figure 4. 8 Beam B2 Load Distribution & Analysis

The maximum bending moment for a fixed ended supported beam is:

$$M = \frac{w * l^2}{12}$$

Eq. 4. 14 Fix ended Maximum Binding Moment

$$M = \frac{2.16 * 4^2}{12} = 2.88 \text{Kn.m}$$

And from design tables we can select the proper section for our project, either I-beam or SHS:

- 1- I-Beam design: we select IPE80 with elastic binding moment resistance of 4.71 KN.m > 2.88 KN.m, therefore IPE80 is safe for B2 beams, with weight =6 Kg/m.
- 2- SHS design: we select SHS 50/4 with elastic binding moment resistance of 2.35 KN.m > 2.16 KN.m, therefore SHS 60/3.2 is safe for B2 Beams, with weight=5.62Kg/m

4.13.3 Design for Beam G[\]

the beam G[\] is a grader beam carrying the Beams B[\] only since Beams B[\] are connected to columns directly these B[\] connected to the grader with distance shown in the figure (4.9) below, the load of Beams B2 shown as P calculated as the following:

$$P = 2.16 \text{ KN/m} \times 4\text{m} / 2 = 4.32 \text{ KN}$$

Figure 4. 9 Beam/Grader G1 Load Distribution & Analysis

And to calculate the maximum bending moment on the Grader G1, we can convert the load into (Simple Supported Beam) since the loads on G1 are Symmetric, the equivalent beam is shown in the figure (10) below:

Figure 4. 10 Beam/Grader G1 Load Distribution & Analysis

And the general equation to calculate the maximum bending moment of simple supported beam with pointed load is:

$$BM = PL/4 = 8.64 \text{ KN} * 5 \text{ m} / 4 = 10.8 \text{ KN.m}$$

And from design tables we can select the proper section for our project, either I-beam or SHS:

- 1- I-Beam design: we select IPE120 with elastic binding moment resistance of 12.45 KN.m > 10.8 KN.m, therefore IPE120 is safe for G1 beams, with weight =10.4 Kg/m.
- 2- SHS design: we select SHS 90/5 with elastic binding moment resistance of 10.42 KN.m > 10.8 KN.m, therefore SHS 90/5 is safe for G1 Beams, with weight=13.1 Kg/m
Total mass of steel structure= column mass + beam mass = (4*2.8) *10.3 + 18*15.5 = 394KG

4.14 Conclusion

1. Structural Safety

The selected structural configuration is engineered to withstand all anticipated loads dead, live, wind, and snow without experiencing material failure or structural instability.

2. Buckling Resistance

Both the vertical columns and inclined beams meet established buckling resistance criteria, ensuring stability under axial and lateral loading conditions.

3. Efficient Load Transfer

The structural system ensures efficient distribution of applied loads. Forces originating from the solar panels are sequentially transmitted to the supporting beams, then to the vertical columns, and ultimately to the reinforced concrete foundations.

4. Maintenance Accessibility

The design incorporates provisions for safe and convenient access, enabling technicians to perform installation, inspection, and maintenance operations without compromising structural integrity.

5. System Scalability

The framework is modular and scalable, allowing for future expansion either by increasing the number of solar panels or by extending the station to accommodate additional EV charging points.

6. Solar Energy Optimization

The orientation and tilt of the PV panels have been optimized to maximize solar exposure throughout daylight hours, thereby enhancing overall energy generation efficiency.

CHAPTER FIVE

**Design and Testing of a
Scalable Solar Charging
Station for EVs and
PHEVs'**

5.1 Introduction

The transition towards renewable energy sources has accelerated the development of solar-powered infrastructure, particularly for (EVs) and (PHEVs).

This project presents a comprehensive methodology for designing, installing and testing and a solar-powered charging the system is conceived to be an off-grid system, in order to meet the needs of EVs and PHEVs regardless of the grid availability, which helps underserved areas or low-quality service to benefit from this design and to be use for new automobile technology in Palestine.

The process with the estimation of power demand and the design of the system with site preparation and foundation work, followed by the assembly of the structural frame and the mounting of solar panels. Subsequently, the installation of inverters and battery systems is performed to ensure efficient energy conversion and storage.

System commissioning involves thorough safety checks and performance verification to guarantee reliable operation.

Finally, the process includes testing the system and verifying its functionality, which proved that the design is applicable and reliable.

These measures aim to sustain long-term performance and maximize energy output. This document systematically addresses each of these.

5.2 Site Preparation and Foundation Work

The actual need for installing a solar-powered charging station has been clearly identified, along with a set of key drivers that formed the basis for moving forward with the project. One of the main motivations is the lack of suitable charging points for electric vehicles within the university campus. In addition, the existing electrical grid suffers from limited coverage in some areas, which affects the stability of power supply. This project also aligns with the university's environmental sustainability goals, as it contributes to reducing harmful emissions and encourages the use of clean energy sources. Another important aspect is the reduction of long-term operational costs by minimizing dependency on conventional energy sources. Moreover, the project serves an educational

and research purpose, providing students with an opportunity to apply theoretical knowledge in a practical, real-world setting within the university.

Although the station design presented in this report is proposed as a reference example, it includes all technical details required for real implementation, and it also allows for future expansion based on demand. Due to the limited available space on campus for installing photovoltaic panels according to the proposed design, the project team obtained official approval to install the system near the university greenhouse. This location was selected for its adequate solar exposure and easy accessibility. The charging point will also be placed nearby to ensure efficient operation

All of these factors helped the team define the system's required capacity, its components, and the step-by-step execution process. Implementation began with proper structural planning, and the chosen installation site was located inside the campus of Palestine Polytechnic University in Hebron. The geographical location directly influences the design decisions, including the orientation and tilt angle of the solar panels, as well as the foundation type. These parameters were previously calculated based on solar irradiance levels and soil characteristics of the selected site.

5.2.1 Site Survey and Assessment

- a. First step involves conducting a detailed site survey to determine optimal location parameters:
- b. Solar Access: The site must have unobstructed access to sunlight for most of the day. Tools such as the Solar Pathfinder or digital solar apps can be used to verify the absence of shading.
- c. Surface Leveling: The land surface is leveled using excavation tools, laser leveling devices, or optical levels to ensure a uniform and horizontal surface across the 4 m x 5 m area. Deviation should not exceed ± 1 cm.
- d. Soil Evaluation: Soil type and compaction are examined through field density tests to determine the suitability for supporting concrete or metallic foundations. Soil bearing capacity must comply with ASTM D2487 standards .
- e. Ground-mount PV systems require compacted soil or concrete bases with sufficient bearing capacity to prevent settlement over time.

5.2.2 Structural Layout & Planning

According to system requirements:

- A- foundation layout consists of four-square steel support legs, anchored at the corners of a 4 m width \times 5 m length rectangular base, shown in the Figure below.

Figure 5. 1 Structure Layout

- B- Six horizontal beams that are to be used to connect the legs: four across the shorter 4 m sides and two running the 5 m length.
- C- The design includes a height of 2.80 m to the panel base and 3.80 m total, allowing for safe pedestrian and vehicle clearance beneath the panels.
- D- For solar panels the tilt angle is set to 30 degree, the optimal angel for Hebron's latitude and the annual average solar insolation to ensure maximum yearly energy yield.

5.2.3 Foundation Installation:

Each structural steel column is designed as a hollow tubular section and anchored to a **reinforced concrete footing** located below the ground surface to maximize usable headroom above. The construction process involves the following sequential steps:

1. **Excavation:** Square pits measuring **60 cm × 60 cm** are excavated at each designated column location, with a depth of approximately **80 cm**. The depth may be modified based on site-specific conditions such as the local frost line and subsurface drainage requirements.
2. **Formwork Installation:** Rigid formwork, constructed from either **plywood or steel panels**, is installed to define the geometry of each footing and ensure dimensional accuracy during concrete casting.
3. **Reinforcement Placement:** A **reinforcement cage** is inserted into each pit to enhance the structural integrity of the footing. The typical configuration consists of **four vertical rebars** and **two horizontal stirrups (rings)**, providing adequate resistance to axial and bending loads.
4. **Concrete Casting:** High-strength concrete of class **C25/30** (characteristic compressive strength = 30 MPa) is poured into the formwork. The mix design conforms to the requirements of **EN 206** or **ASTM C94** standards, ensuring durability and load-bearing capacity under static and dynamic loading conditions.

After the concrete has undergone full curing, **anchor bolts** are installed at the center of each footing to secure the steel columns. These anchors may either be **chemically bonded post-curing** or **pre-embedded** during the concrete pouring phase, depending on the selected construction technique.

After completing the concrete foundation curing process and verifying the positioning of the anchor bolts, the next phase involves assembling and installing the structural steel frame that will support the solar panels.

5.2.4 Mounting Rails and Tilt Angle Adjustment

Steel mounting rails are affixed to the upper steel beams using mechanical clamps or bolted connections, serving as the structural base for the photovoltaic (PV) modules.

These rails are inclined at an angle of 30°, based on site-specific solar optimization for the Hebron region, to maximize annual solar irradiance capture.

As illustrated in Figure 5.2, the PV modules are to be installed atop an existing greenhouse structure, which provides a viable surface for module deployment.

To ensure precise alignment, inclination brackets or adjustable tilt joints are utilized. These components facilitate fine-tuning of the tilt angle to account for construction tolerances or seasonal solar variations

Figure 5. 2 The greenhouse on which the solar panels are to be installed

- Inclination brackets or adjustable joints allow fine-tuning the tilt angle

Mounting of Solar Panels and Electrical DC Wirin As we mentioned, due to the limited space in the we will use the greenhouse to carry the solar panels.

Figure 5. 3: Another picture of the greenhouse where the solar panels.

5.3 Mounting the Solar Panels

We have successfully installed the steel mounting profiles that will support the photovoltaic panels on top of the greenhouse structure. To ensure maximum structural integrity and long-term safety, we employed precision welding techniques at all key joints. This approach was chosen over mechanical fasteners to enhance the load-bearing capacity, minimize potential vibrations under wind loads, and guarantee a secure foundation for the solar array installation, as shown in the figure4.

Figure 5. 4 Installing profiles above the greenhouse

The PV modules used in this installation are mounted directly onto the rails using mid clamps and end clamps, which ensure a secure and durable fixation

These clamps are chosen to match the thickness of the PV panel frames and allow for thermal expansion without loosening.

Each solar panel is aligned with the previously measured spacing and installed from one side to the other to maintain a continuous electrical connection along the string. Panel grounding is achieved either through the clamp design itself or using grounding lugs connected to the rail.

5.3.1 Electrical Wiring – Series and Parallel Connections

Once the physical mounting is complete, the next step is interconnecting the PV modules. The panels are wired in series to form strings, each producing a higher voltage suitable for the input range of the inverter. The number of modules per string is determined based on:

- The inverter's maximum input voltage

- The open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}) of each panel that accord say to manufacture data
- Expected temperature variations (as V_{oc} increases in cold conditions)

Figure 5. 5 Two PV modules connected in Series using MC4 multibranch connectors.

Multiple strings can be connected in parallel using a DC combiner box to achieve the required current. Cables used must be UV-resistant and double-insulated, complying with IEC 62930 standards.

The panels were installed over the profiles that were welded to the roof of the greenhouse, as shown in the following figure

Figure 5. 6 After installing solar panels on top of the greenhouse

5.3.2 Cable Management and Protection

Wiring is routed through cable trays or conduits mounted underneath the rails. UV-rated cable ties are used for neat bundling. All connections are protected to ensure durability and safety in outdoor installations. Weatherproof connectors (MC4-type) are used; these are standardized connectors widely adopted in photovoltaic systems due to their IP67 rating, which provides resistance to water and dust. Inline fuses or

string fuses are integrated into each positive conductor within the combiner box to protect against overcurrent. Additionally, surge protection devices (SPDs) and DC circuit breakers are included to safeguard the system from overvoltage and fault currents, as shown in Figure.

Figure 5. 7Trays to protect wires from external influences

5.4 Installation of the Inverter and Battery System

Upon completing the mechanical mounting of the photovoltaic modules and the routing of the DC electrical wiring, the subsequent phase involves the installation of the **inverter** and the **battery energy storage system (BESS)**. These components serve critical roles in system functionality: the **inverter** converts the direct current (DC) electricity generated by the solar panels into alternating current (AC) power suitable for household or commercial loads, while the **battery storage unit** stores surplus energy for use during periods of low or no solar generation.

Furthermore, as illustrated in the **circuit diagram** obtained from the equipment datasheet, all electrical interconnections were executed strictly according to an **off-grid system configuration**. This means that the wiring and system setup were designed exclusively for **standalone operation**, without any specified manufacturer guidelines for off-grid integration, ensuring

compatibility and operational reliability under autonomous conditions connection to the public utility grid. The implementation adheres to the.

Figure 5. 8 Circuit for connecting batteries and solar cells to the inverter

5.4.1 Inverter Placement and Mounting

We installed and securely mounted the inverter inside a protective enclosure on the front wall of Yaffa Library. The selected location provides shade and proper ventilation to prevent overheating and ensure safe operation.

Installation was carried out in accordance with the manufacturer's recommendations, maintaining the required clearances around the unit to allow for adequate airflow and ease of maintenance.

A string inverter was used in this system, connected directly to the configured PV strings. To ensure durability in outdoor conditions, the inverter was enclosed in an box, offering protection against dust and water.

As shown in the following figure, the inverter was professionally installed and mounted as per the design guidelines.

Figure 5. 9 Inverter after installation inside the box

5.4.2 DC to AC Conversion and Off-Grid Operation

The inverter is responsible for converting the high-voltage DC electricity generated by the solar panels into usable AC power.

Based on the following wiring diagram, which was taken directly from the manufacturer's datasheet, we connected the entire system to operate solely in an off-grid mode. No grid-tied configuration was used—only the off-grid setup was implemented, exactly as shown in the diagram.

Figure 5. 10 Wiring diagram inside the inverter

5.4.3 Wiring and Protection Components

The following electrical wiring and protection components were installed to ensure the system's safety and reliability:

DC Disconnect: Installed between the PV panels and the inverter to allow safe isolation during maintenance

Surge Protectors: Installed on both the DC and AC sides to protect the system from transient overvoltage such as lightning-induced surges.

Grounding: Both the inverter and battery storage system were grounded in full compliance with NEC and IEC standards.

All of these components including wiring terminals, protection devices, and disconnect switches were installed next to the inverter, within the same weatherproof enclosure.

This integrated configuration ensures a compact layout, simplifies maintenance, and provides additional protection against environmental conditions such as dust and moisture, in line with IP65 standards

5.4.4 EV Charger Integration

In addition to grid integration, the AC output from the inverter is directly routed to a 7 kW electric vehicle (EV) charger installed within the same wall-mounted enclosure on the front wall of the Yafa Library adjacent to the greenhouse. The charger is wired through an AC circuit breaker to ensure protection against overcurrent and short circuits. Synchronization between the inverter and charger ensures that vehicle charging prioritizes direct solar energy usage when available, reducing dependency on grid power.

5.4.5 Battery Storage System

For the storage component, we utilized a repurposed Hyundai Ioniq electric vehicle battery, selected for its high efficiency and proven reliability. This battery system allows surplus AC energy, generated during peak sunlight hours when the EV charger is not in use, to be stored and later deployed during periods of high demand or at night.

To ensure safe and efficient operation, the battery is paired with a dedicated battery management system (BMS) that continuously monitors charge levels, temperature, and discharge rates, preventing overcharging, deep discharges, or thermal risks.

As shown in the figure 7, both the battery and the BMS have been installed inside a specially designed, insulated enclosure located on the rear (hidden) side of the Yafa Library, away from student pathways and daily campus activities. This placement was carefully chosen to minimize exposure to accidental impacts or tampering, aligning with best practices for safety in public or semi-public installations.

Figure 5. 11 Storage batteries and battery management system

5.4.6 Comprehensive Wiring and Protection

The entire system includes:

- Dedicated DC and AC disconnect switches for safe maintenance.
- Surge protection devices (SPDs) on all key DC and AC lines.
- Waterproof combiner boxes inside the wall-mounted enclosure to house fuses and wiring junctions, ensuring protection against water ingress and environmental exposure.
- Grounding and bonding connections linking the inverter, charger, battery system, and metal enclosure to a shared grounding electrode, complying with NEC and IEC standards.

5.5 Safety and Protection Measures

To ensure the highest level of safety and protection for both the system and its surroundings, we implemented a comprehensive set of safety measures covering fire protection, thermal management, electrical safety, and physical security.

Specifically, both the inverter/EV charger enclosure and the battery storage cabinet were equipped with automatic heat-activated fire extinguishers, as shown in Figure 8. Unlike standard handheld extinguishers, these advanced devices are mounted at the top of each cabinet and are designed to detect internal temperature rises. When the air temperature inside the enclosure reaches a preset threshold, they automatically release a fire-suppressing agent, ensuring immediate response to any fire without the need for human intervention.

Figure 5. 12 automatic heat-activated fire extinguishers

In addition, two cooling fans were installed inside the inverter and charger enclosure to actively manage heat buildup during operation, reducing the risk of overheating and thermal stress. Temperature sensors monitor the system in real-time and can trigger automatic shutdown if unsafe conditions are detected.

The battery system is managed by an integrated Battery Management System (BMS), which continuously oversees the charge levels, temperature, and health of the battery modules. The BMS plays a critical role in preventing overcharging, deep discharges, and thermal events, further enhancing the system's operational safety. Moreover, the battery cabinet was designed with sufficient internal space to allow for natural airflow and heat dissipation, providing an additional passive cooling layer alongside active thermal management strategies.

Figure 5. 13 BMS

For maximum safety, an emergency switch (emergency cutoff) was installed to allow complete system shutdown in case of a detected fault or hazardous event. This switch provides a manual, quick-access solution to instantly disconnect all system components from both DC and AC sources, protecting equipment and personnel during critical situations.

Figure 5. 14 emergency switch

Electrical safety measures also include surge protection devices (SPDs) on both DC and AC lines, dedicated disconnect switches for routine maintenance, and properly rated fuses and circuit breakers to prevent overcurrent or short circuits. All system components are carefully grounded and bonded in full compliance with NEC and IEC standards, minimizing the risk of electrical hazards.

From a physical safety standpoint, all enclosures are isolated and insulated, with the battery and BMS placed in a separate cabinet away from the inverter and charger. These enclosures are installed on the hidden rear side of the Yafa Library, away from student pathways, minimizing exposure to accidental impact or tampering. Weatherproof (IP65/IP67-rated) enclosures and connectors further protect against environmental exposure, and clear safety signage has been installed to guide users and maintenance staff in emergencies.

Together, these carefully planned measures create a robust multi-layered safety framework, ensuring the system operates reliably, safely, and in full compliance with international standards.

5.6 Final Integration and System Testing

Figure 5. 15 Final charger connectivity

After the complete installation of the photovoltaic system including the solar panels, inverter, battery storage, wiring, and protection components we proceeded with the final integration phase, which involved connecting the dedicated EV charger to the system. The charger was properly wired to draw power from the inverter's AC output, ensuring compatibility with the off-grid configuration.

Once all components were securely connected and double-checked for safety, we performed a full operational system test, during which an electric vehicle was successfully charged using the solar-generated and battery-stored energy. The test confirmed that the system operates reliably and delivers sufficient power for EV charging under real-world conditions.

Figure 5. 16 The vehicle during the shipping process

Figure 5. 17 The vehicle after the charging process

As shown in the following figure, the setup illustrates the completed system with the EV charger connected and actively delivering power to the vehicle. This marks a significant milestone in the implementation, demonstrating not only the correctness of the electrical design but also the practical functionality of the system as an independent, solar-powered EV charging solution.

Figure 5. 18 Final Vehicle Charging Setup

5.7 Maintenance Guidelines and Operational recommendations

Proper maintenance ensures the longevity and efficient operation of the solar PV system. Routine inspections and preventive measures minimize downtime and prevent costly repairs.

5.7.1 Routine Visual Inspections Visual checks should be performed monthly and include:

- Checking for dirt accumulation or shading on panels.
- Inspecting panel surfaces for cracks or delamination.
- Verifying integrity of mechanical supports and mounting structures.
- Checking for signs of corrosion, loose bolts, or misalignment.

5.7.2 Electrical System Monitoring

- Review inverter data logs weekly for unusual patterns.
- Monitor string voltages and currents to identify imbalances.
- Check surge protection devices and fuses for proper operation.
- Validate grounding resistance annually using appropriate testing equipment.

5.7.3 Cleaning of Solar Panels

- Clean panels at least twice a year or more frequently if the environment is dusty.
- Use soft brushes or sponges with deionized water.
- Avoid abrasive materials or high-pressure washing that could damage panel surfaces.

5.7.4 Preventive Maintenance of Inverter and Batteries

- Inspect inverter ventilation fans and filters.

- Check battery electrolyte levels (if applicable) or battery management system (BMS) status.
- Update inverter firmware as per manufacturer recommendations.
- Perform system shutdown and restart tests every six months to ensure emergency procedures are functional

User Manual

1. This solar-powered EV charging station has been designed to ensure a safe, efficient, and user-friendly experience. To operate the system correctly, please follow the steps below:
2. **System Activation:** Ensure the photovoltaic (PV) panels are properly connected to the inverter and that the battery bank has a sufficient state of charge. Power on the inverter (Deye unit) using the main switch located on its front panel.
3. **Vehicle Connection:** Once the inverter is operational, plug the EV charging cable into the vehicle's charging port. Ensure the vehicle is parked safely before initiating the charging process.
4. **Performance Monitoring:** Use the inverter's digital display screen to monitor key operational parameters such as input/output voltage, current levels, battery state of charge, and energy flow status. Regular monitoring during the charging session is recommended.
5. **Alerts and Warnings:** If any warning indicators appear on the screen or if an audible alert is triggered by the inverter or the EV charger, immediately shut down the system and inspect the source of the error before continuing.
6. **Safe Operation Guidelines:** Avoid connecting additional loads to the inverter during EV charging. Do not expose the charging cable or connectors to water or humid environments. Internal components must not be tampered with unless by certified technicians.

Recommendations

1. **Implementation of a Smart Charging System**

It is recommended to incorporate a smart charging unit equipped with advanced features such as programmable scheduling, real-time energy consumption

tracking, and remote access capabilities through mobile or web-based platforms. These functionalities contribute to improved energy efficiency, better load management, and enhanced user convenience.

2. Integration of a User Display Interface

The system should include a digital display interface or touchscreen panel that provides real-time information such as charging status, total energy delivered, and estimated time to full charge. This enhances the user experience by improving transparency and usability during the charging process.

3. Scalability and Infrastructure Planning for Future Expansion

The electrical and structural design should be developed with future scalability in mind. This includes provisioning for additional chargers or outlets, and ensuring that wiring, distribution panels, and protection devices are dimensioned to accommodate increased electrical loads as demand grows over time.

4. Development of a Mobile Application for Monitoring and Control

It is advised to develop a dedicated mobile application that enables users to remotely monitor and interact with the EV charging station. The application would communicate with the system via Wi-Fi, Bluetooth, or cellular connectivity, depending on the site's available infrastructure. The app should offer the following features:

- Real-time display of battery state of charge (SOC).
- Estimated time to full charge.
- Cumulative energy consumption measured in kilowatt-hours (kWh).
- Access to daily and weekly charging logs.
- Push notifications for completed charging sessions or fault detection.

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Appendix A: Technical Datasheet – Jinko Solar Panel (570-590 Wp)

The following document presents the technical specifications of the Jinko solar panel used in this project. The datasheet includes electrical characteristics, mechanical dimensions, efficiency, and thermal coefficients. This document was obtained from the official source provided by Jinko Solar.

www.jinkosolar.com

TIGER Neo

72HL4-BDV

570-590 Watt
BIFACIAL MODULE WITH DUAL GLASS

N-type

 N-type Technology
N-type modules with Tunnel Oxide Passivating Contacts (TOPCon) technology offer lower LID/LeTID degradation and better low light performance.

 HOT 2.0 Technology
N-type modules with JinkoSolar's HOT 2.0 technology offer better reliability and efficiency.

 Dual-Sided Power Generation
Dual-sided power generation gain increases with backside exposure to light, significantly reducing LCOE.

 Mechanical Load Enhanced
Certified to withstand:
5400 Pa front side max static test load
2400 Pa rear side max static test load

 SMBB Technology
Better light trapping and current collection to improve module power output and reliability.

 Anti-PID Guarantee
Minimizes the chance of degradation caused by PID phenomena through optimization of cell production technology and material control.

12 Year Product Warranty | **30 Year** Linear Power Warranty | **1%** First year Degradation | **0.4%** Annual Degradation Over 30 Years

- IEC61215 (2016) / IEC61730 (2016)
- IEC61701 / IEC62716 / IEC60068 / IEC62804
- ISO9001:2015: Quality Management System
- ISO14001:2015: Environment Management System
- ISO45001:2018: Occupational health and safety management systems

JKM570-590N-72HL4-BDV-F8-EN

72HL4-BDV 570-590 Watt

Mechanical Characteristics

Cell Type	N-type Mono-crystalline
No. of cells	144 (72×2)
Dimensions	2278×1134×30 mm
Weight	31.0 kg
Front Glass	2.0 mm, Anti-Reflection Coating
Back Glass	2.0 mm, Heat Strengthened Glass
Frame	Anodized Aluminium Alloy
Junction Box	IP68 Rated
Protection Class	Class II
IEC Fire Type	Class C
Output Cables	4.0 mm ² (+): 400 mm , (-): 200 mm or Customized Length

Packaging Configuration

Pallet Dimensions	2338×1140×1251 mm
Packing Detail (Two pallets - One stack)	36 pcs/pallets, 72 pcs/stack, 720 pcs/ 40'HQ Container

Specifications (STC)

Maximum Power - Pmax [Wp]	570	575	580	585	590
Maximum Power Voltage - Vmp [V]	43.58	43.73	43.88	44.02	44.17
Maximum Power Current - Imp [A]	13.08	13.15	13.22	13.29	13.36
Open-circuit Voltage - Voc [V]	52.10	52.30	52.50	52.70	52.90
Short-circuit Current - Isc [A]	13.83	13.89	13.95	14.01	14.07
Module Efficiency STC [%]	22.07	22.26	22.45	22.65	22.84
Power Tolerance	0 ~ +3%				
Temperature Coefficients of Pmax	-0.29 %/°C				
Temperature Coefficients of Voc	-0.25 %/°C				
Temperature Coefficients of Isc	0.045 %/°C				

STC: Irradiance 1000W/m², Cell Temperature 25°C, AM-1.5

Specifications (NOCT)

Maximum Power - Pmax [Wp]	430	433	437	441	445
Maximum Power Voltage - Vmp [V]	40.56	40.73	40.89	41.05	41.21
Maximum Power Current - Imp [A]	10.59	10.64	10.69	10.74	10.79
Open-circuit Voltage - Voc [V]	49.49	49.68	49.87	50.06	50.25
Short-circuit Current - Isc [A]	11.16	11.21	11.26	11.31	11.36

NOCT: Irradiance 800W/m², Ambient Temperature 20°C, AM-1.5, Wind Speed 1m/s

Application Conditions

Operating Temperature	-40 °C ~ +85 °C
Maximum System Voltage	1500 VDC (IEC)
Maximum Series Fuse Rating	30 A
Nominal Operating Cell Temperature -NOCT	45±2 °C
Refer. Bifacial Factor	80±5 %

Engineering Drawings

Electrical Performance

No.1, Lane 1466, Shen Chang Road, Minhang District, Shanghai, China
Tel: +86-21-51808777 Fax: +86-21-51808600 www.jinkosolar.com

JKM570-590N-72HL4-BDV-F8-EN

NOTE: Please read the safety and installation manual before using the product.
We reserve the right of final interpretation. The specifications in this datasheet are subject to change without notice.